

SETTLEMENT, SOCIETY AND POLITY IN EARLY MEDIEVAL RURAL INDIA

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India is made up of villages—thousands and thousands of them. It is more appropriate to use the plural rather than the singular which suggests a misleading image of ‘the typical’ Indian village, enclosed in its little community, surviving as an intangible, unchanging and always self-sufficient unit, throughout the eventful history of India; and which also seems to suggest that by some second miracle, ‘the village’ was the same throughout the huge subcontinent....

These words from Fernand Braudel¹ could serve as a fitting Foreword to B.D. Chattopadhyaya’s *Aspects of Rural Settlements and Rural Society in Early Medieval India*² (henceforth *Aspects*).³ The slimness of this volume belies its importance, which can be properly appreciated only through an extended discussion. With the village as the primary unit of social organization as its central theme, it is a microscopic study of three areas : Bengal during Gupta and post-Gupta periods; the two tehsils of Pali district in Rajasthan as the domain of the Cāhamānas of Naḍḍula; and the history of village Kalikatṭi in South Karnataka during Hoysaḷa period.

The *Aspects* is an *analysis* of the source material from these three areas to make some general points. It has not been Chattopadhyaya’s intention to provide here a full-blown picture of the early medieval Indian countryside, not lacking in general respects, such as the ones provided by R.S. Sharma, D.D. Kosambi and Burton Stein. His has been “essentially ... a plea to the undertaking of research” (p. 125) on “rural settlements and rural society” as “specific themes” (p. 10). It is in his latest “The Making of Early Medieval India”⁴ that we see a *synthesis* of these points with his reading of the other aspects of early medieval Indian history to give us a general picture of the times.

Neither in the *Aspects* nor in “The Making” does he provide a detailed critique of the historiography. That is not his “primary intention”, he states (*ibid.*)⁵. The critique is not detailed, yet of critical importance as it consists of a set of emphatic judgements on the major strands of the historiography. To follow Chattopadhyaya is thus to follow the key themes in the current historiography, and the departures therefrom.

The present article is a response to the above. It seeks to (i) highlight the historical points made in the *Aspects*; (ii) present a critique of some of them by offering alternative readings of

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- 1 Fernand Braudel, *Civilization and Capitalism: 15th-18th Century*, Vol. III, *The Perspective of the World*, tr. from the French by Siân Reynolds (Fontana/Collins, London, 1988), p. 498.
 - 2 S.G. Deuskar Lectures on Indian History and Culture, 1985 (K.P. Bagchi & Company, Calcutta, 1990).
 - 3 The paginations in the text refer to the *Aspects*, unless otherwise specified.
 - 4 “The Making of Early Medieval India”, Introduction in B.D. Chattopadhyaya, *The Making of Early Medieval India* (Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 1994), pp. 1-37.
 - 5 Also *ibid.*, p. 14.

the evidence; (iii) use the data in the *Aspects* to make some additional points; and (iv) comprehend the precise ways in which Chattopadhyaya's findings may be related to the existing knowledge and situated in our general understanding of early medieval India. The last exercise is undertaken separately at the end; the first three move cheek by jowl as we follow Chattopadhyaya—and his predecessors in his wake—on geography, polity and society in successive order.

1 Settlement

A major concern of Chattopadhyaya is rural settlement geography. He shows in detail how the dominant landmarks in rural Bengal were "surface sources of water"—rivers, riverlets, channels and ponds (pp. 29-34); in south-east Marwar were wells (pp. 72-76); and at Kalikaṭṭi in South Karnataka were tanks (pp. 95, 97-100). The author underlines these contrasts time and again (pp. 12, 33, 77, 100) to bring out "distinctions between rural settlements of different regions", corresponding to the geographical differences (p. 12).

1.1 Agrarian expansion and colonization

The data in the *Aspects* allow us to make another comparative exercise in the different modes of agrarian expansion in early medieval India. In Bengal, the Tippera plate of Lokanātha and the Paschimbhag plates of Śricandra show how large groups of brāhmaṇas were settled by the state in uninhabited areas (pp. 26, 28-29, 32, 55). In south-east Marwar, the *Purātanaprabandhasaṅgraha* suggests "the colonization of a tribal tract by a ruling family which needed to expand" (pp. 71-72). At Kalikaṭṭi, the unit of agrarian expansion seems to have been small plot of land, and the significant variable was artificial irrigation, which required substantial investment but brought adequate returns by converting dry land (*beḍdale*) into wet land (*gardde*). Such expansion occurred through both state and private initiative (pp. 95, 97-99). Sometimes a person could be resourceful enough to open not just a plot but an entire tract to cultivation, as when Hoḍeya Biṭṭeya set up around 1208-9 a hamlet (*halli*) after his own name (pp. 99-100). This *halli* was made a part of Kalikaṭṭi (ibid.). This process of the expansion of Kalikaṭṭi's agrarian space (and probably the initial formation of Kalikaṭṭi itself) through the gradual accumulation of plots and hamlets could then be contrasted with the process evidenced in the Paschimbhag plates, when a huge area was opened to cultivation through donation to six thousand brāhmaṇas in six thousand plots.

However, I am not sure if we could use the evidence of the Paschimbhag plates and the *Purātanaprabandhasaṅgraha* for the expansion of agrarian space by six thousand brāhmaṇas and the colonization of a tribal tract. The Paschimbhag record describes the grant of one hundred and twenty *pāṭakas* of land to one set of gods and two hundred and eighty *pāṭakas* of land to another set. These tracts are then broken down into plots of specific measures and granted to specific personnel.⁶ This fact and that no prior possessors of these plots are mentioned leave little doubt that these were uncultivated areas. These two tracts were situated in a *brahmapura* called Candrapura which was constituted of three *viṣayas*: Garali *viṣaya*, Pogara *viṣaya* and

⁶ D.C. Sircar, *Epigraphic Discoveries in East Pakistan* (Calcutta, 1973), pp. 67-68, ll. 36-47 (lines always represent text lines).

Candrapura *viṣaya*.⁷ The rest of these three *viṣayas* was granted in *equal shares*⁸ to six thousand *brāhmaṇas*, and we have reasons to suppose that this meant equal share of the revenue from this area, and not the division of this area into equal plots. That the grant was made according to *bhūmicchidranyāya* suggests to Chattopadhyaya that the area was uncultivated (p. 55). But this is not necessary, as Sharma has frequently emphasized.⁹ In our case, the fact that Candrapura *brahmapura* was divided into three *viṣayas* is a reliable indicator that it was already settled in good measure, for the drawing of administrative boundaries would not occur in desolate tracts. The existence of a boat-station area of considerable dimension, which was excluded from the grant, points to the same, as does the exclusion of the land which was (already) granted to the Buddhists (*ratnatrayabhūmivarjītāḥ*).¹⁰ The clincher: the grant was addressed to state functionaries, *brāhmaṇas* and cultivators of the area. These *brāhmaṇas* and cultivators were asked at the end of the grant to be obedient to the donees and regularly pay them due taxes.¹¹

For Marwar too, there is enough evidence of a flourishing state society in the records of the Rāṣṭrakūṭa king Dhavala of Hastikuṇḍin in Godwad region itself in close proximity to the future domain of the Naḍḍula Cāhamānas. Chattopadhyaya notes this (pp. 71-72) and brings it in line with his reading of the *Purātanaprabandhasaṅgraha* by postulating that “the upper parts of the Godwad plain” were not a part of the neighbouring state society, but “offered sufficient attraction for a fresh team of colonizers” (p. 72). In our opinion, however, the *Purātanaprabandhasaṅgraha* describes a non-tribal population of *brāhmaṇas* and others being harassed by the Mers rather than a tribal tract peopled by the Mers.¹² There is a gap of about a hundred years between “the establishment of the Nadol Cāhamāna kingdom by Lakṣmaṇa” and the appearance of “the earliest inscriptional records of any importance” (p. 73). Chattopadhyaya suggests that the intervening period was marked by the process of “the crystallization of rural settlements” (*ibid.*), a logical inference from the postulate of the colonization of a tribal tract. However, the Bhadund stone inscription of the Paramāras of Candrāvati, Vikrama year 1102, shows that the Bali tehsil was controlled by the Paramāras during this gap about the mid-eleventh century.¹³ It would seem that there was a kind of political vacuum in the area, probably created by the end of Rāṣṭrakūṭa rule, of which Lakṣmaṇa, the Mers and the Paramāras sought to take advantage; the political disturbance became protracted and ended only with the emergence of the Cāhamānas as the final victors.

1.2 The layout of settlements in early medieval Bengal

A particular concern of Chattopadhyaya is rural settlement patterns in early medieval Bengal. The frame of reference is a controversy between the geographers O.H.K. Spate and A.T.A. Learmonth on the one hand and the historians on the other. The former stated that “the settlement

7 *Ibid.*, pp. 66-67, ll. 27-28, 35-36.

8 *samavibhāgena śeṣabhūmiḥ*, *ibid.*, p. 67, l. 51.

9 *Indian Feudalism c. A.D. 300-1200*, 2nd edn (Macmillan, Delhi, 1980), pp. 29-32; *Urban Decay in India, (c. 300-c. 1000)* (Munshiram Manoharlal, New Delhi, 1987), p. 169.

10 Sircar, *Epigraphic Discoveries*, p. 68, l. 54.

11 *Ibid.*, ll. 56-57.

12 Muni Jinavijaya, ed, *The Purātanaprabandhasaṅgraha* (Singhi Jain Granthamala, Santi Niketan, 1936), pp. 101-2.

13 H.V. Trivedi, ed, *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. VII, Pt 2, No. 63, pp. 232-37.

pattern of much of Bengal (especially the East) is distinctive in that the homestead, and not the compact village, is the unit". The historians' understanding has been just the opposite: "... as far as available evidence indicates, they [the villages] were of the nucleated, not of the single farm type. That is to say, the rural population lived in compact groups and not in widely scattered habitations".¹⁴

Chattopadhyaya underlines the slenderness of the historical evidence, "contrary to the impression generated by the historians" (p. 24). Nevertheless his own analysis supports them against the geographers. He brings out the evidence for *clusters* of severally held plots of cultivated land (pp. 21-24). These clusters negate the possibility of a unity of homestead and farmland, "a separable unity of *vāstu* and *kṣetra*" (p. 21). They tell us no further about "the pattern or the distribution of residential plots" (p. 22). The vital thing is: "If this evidence is taken to reconstruct the area of village habitat, then the impression is likely to be that of a compact, nucleated settlement" (p. 24, also p. 21). The generalization: "The rural settlements of the Gupta period, mostly located in North Bengal, but as evidence from the later period shows, extending toward the east, seem thus to have been compact villages occurring within clusters of similar villages" (p. 24).

In fact, the historians and the geographers have been at cross-purposes. Spate and Learmonth never meant that in Bengal each homestead had a surrounding farmland bordering on other such homestead-farmland units, which Chattopadhyaya and others seek to disprove. Actually the former reject it for most of India in a graphic description:

The great majority of the country folk [in India and Pakistan] live in small or large nucleated settlements, and areas of dispersed habitations are few: the Himalayan zone is perhaps the only extensive area of true dispersal, of the type found in European highlands; elsewhere even in the hills, the normal unit is the small hamlet rather than the homestead.... The Bengal Delta—especially in the East—is *sui generis*: there is indeed much settlement that is not nucleated, but "dispersal" appears an exceedingly inappropriate term for *the dense stipple of separate homesteads*, hardly isolated except in the most literal sense of the word when, during the rains, each is an isolated island on its little earthen plinth.¹⁵

This peculiarity of the Bengal countryside along with the variations from it is described in greater detail on pp. 590-91, but it is the two figures 19.6(p. 580) and 19.7(p. 584) that convey it best, showing how *vāstu* areas were distinct from *kṣetra* areas without being nucleated.

The second point against the historians' reconstruction is that the spatial distinction between the habitation area and the cultivated area would hold good—and so would not tell us—whether the habitation area was nucleated or linear or ringed or clusters of homesteads which Spate and Learmonth describe as the dominant pattern for Bengal.

The other contributions of Chattopadhyaya to Bengal's historical geography seem unexceptionable. First, the details in the Vappaghoṣavāṭa grant of Jayanāga hint at "the linear nucleation of habitation units" (pp. 24-25, though I would not use the term "nucleation"). The other variations in the settlement pattern would derive from the influence of terrain and mode of

14 Both cited by the author, p. 20.

15 O.H.K. Spate and A.T.A. Learmonth, *India and Pakistan: A General and Regional Geography*, 3rd edn (Methuen & Co. Ltd, Suffolk, 1967), p. 180, emphasis added.

cultivation, the process of colonization of new areas and the settlement of an area by a small community (pp. 25-29). All this finds a happy convergence with the descriptions of Spate and Learmonth. Second, the details of the individuals holding the plots of a village give us "a glimpse into the social character of the *vāstu* component of a village" (p. 7). That is how the Paschimbhag plates enable us to visualize "the domineering presence of a sizeable *brāhmaṇa* population" in Candrapura *brahmapura* (p. 29) and the Sunderban plate of the time of Lakṣmaṇasena suggests "a domineering presence of official elements in the affairs of [the village] Kāntallapura *caturaka*" (p. 36), while the plots in the Gunaighar inscription (pp. 23-24) reveal "a wide social cross-section" (p. 24). Apart from plots, place-names also offer clues. Thus the village *Vārāyipada-grāma*, "the habitation of the Barayi (betel-vine growers)", "would seem to have been associated with a particular community, and, therefore, was of an internal structure different from settlements which had a more heterogeneous social composition" (p. 28).

The paginations in the preceding paragraph help to underline the complex nature of some of the presentation: the meaning of the general statement on p. 7 can be grasped only through the specific illustrations on pp. 23-24, 28, 29 and 36, which occur in disparate contexts, unrelated to each other and to the general point. At the same time, it is obvious that taking Chattopadhyaya seriously has its rewards.

On p. 35 Chattopadhyaya states: "The spatial characteristics of rural settlements could, in many ways, be related to the manner in which rural communities were organized". The relation between social organization and settlement is not elaborated or illustrated, so that the significance of the statement is not immediately obvious. But we could reconstruct at least one such relation from his scattered remarks. On p. 26 we read: "... the nature of relations between social groups present in it [that is, a newly created settlement] was likely to be somewhat different from that in settlements which had evolved over a long period of time". A newly created settlement, *brahmapura* called Candrapura, is described in detail (pp. 55-57, 67-69) and it is noted in passing that it was "a society with a largely pre-determined structure" (p. 56). Trying to understand the statement on p. 26, we now see how differently organized this society was from that in older villages (pp. 35-55). This contrast in social structure can be seen to correspond to that in the settlement pattern: Chattopadhyaya demonstrates how Candrapura *brahmapura* was "too extensive to have evolved as an average village settlement" (pp. 28-29) while the average settlement was nucleated (pp. 21-24). Apparently Chattopadhyaya wrote the statement on p. 35 with something like this at the back of his mind. Our doubt whether the average village was nucleated does not affect this, for the point here is the *contrast* in settlement pattern, and there can be little doubt that the layout of the expansive temple-*maṭha* complexes was dissimilar to that of the average village. Only the manner of settlement of six thousand *brāhmaṇas*, if we accept that they did not colonize uncultivated terrain but were granted revenues of settled areas, remains unknown to us, and hence does not bear on the issue. This exercise in social geography, then, would be the historian's contribution to the work on the relation between settlement type and socio-political set-up done by other social scientists.¹⁶

16 For example, Joan Mencher, "Kerala and Madras: A Comparative Study of Ecology and Social Structure", *Ethnology*, Vol. V (1966), pp. 135-79, reproduced in Ram Guha, ed, *Social Ecology* (Oxford University Press, Delhi, 1994), pp. 42-81; Ralph W. Nicholas, "Ecology and Village Structure in Deltaic West Bengal", *The Economic Weekly*, Vol. XV (1963), pp. 1185-96; David G. Mandelbaum, *Society in India* (Popular Prakashan, Bombay, 1972), pp. 337-41, 343-44, 405-9, 579-80.

2 Polity

The dominant theme in these lectures is “the changing relationship between political authority and the village” (p. 36). In each case study, different aspects of the theme are pursued.

2.1 The Bengal countryside : Chattopadhyaya’s interpretation of the evidence

For Bengal Chattopadhyaya identifies three phases of this relationship: middle Gupta period, sixth-seventh centuries and early Pāla period.

During the Gupta period, land-sale inscriptions show the representatives of different rural groups—*kuṭumbins*, *brāhmaṇas*, *mahattaras*, etc.—participating in local administration. There were two official bodies (*adhikaraṇas*) above the village functioning separately in different areas: *grāmāṣṭakulādhikaraṇa* and *vīthyadhikaraṇa*. It is important that the rural representatives were associated with these *adhikaraṇas* but did not constitute them (pp. 37, 39, 40, 43). Second, a comparison of the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur inscription with the Jagdishpur plate, both records being from the same locality and separated by just about eight years, shows wide variations in the number and categories of the representatives. The Kalaikuri-Sultanpur record has the names of seven *kāyasthas*, one *vīthi-kulika*, two *pustapālas*, eight *vīthi-mahattaras* and seventy-six *kuṭumbins*; the Jagdishpur inscription has the names of only four *vīthi-mahattaras* and twenty-eight *kuṭumbins*, and no *vīthi-kulika*, *kāyastha* or *pustapāla* (pp. 40-41). The twin observations lead on to the following conclusions: it is improbable that these persons made up “a formal elective rural body, with a fixed number of representatives” (p. 43); “local community participation was not a rigidly structured system interacting with the Gupta system of administration” (p. 41); and the “rural communities did not represent formal bodies but were informally structured groups...” (pp. 43-44).

The fact that these rural representatives, acting in association with the *adhikaraṇas*, are mentioned by name in these land-sale charters shows that before land in a village could be alienated, the consent of the various categories of villagers had to be obtained (pp. 37, 40). An important aspect of their participation was in the measurement of land; the Damodarpur copper plate of the time of Budhagupta (A.D. 482-83) shows that the land for sale was measured by “*mahattaras* and others, officers and householders (*mahattarādyadhikaraṇakuṭumbibhiḥ*)” (pp. 37-38). Then the Baigram record lays down that the land for sale should be so located as not to disturb the people’s own area of cultivation (*svakarṣaṇāvirodhisthāne*) (p. 44). All this would show how “the Gupta state accommodated the rural landed interests down to the level of individual villages” (ibid.).

There was no rural representation during the middle Gupta period at the higher administrative level of *viśaya*. This is seen in the composition of the *viśayādhikaraṇa* of Koṭivarṣa: one official head *kumārāmātya* and “representatives from four non-agriculturist occupational groups: *prathama-kulika* (the chief artisan), *prathama-kāyastha* (the chief scribe), *sārthavāha* (the merchant) and *nagara-śreṣṭhin* (the guild-president of the town)” (pp. 39-40).

Finally, the composition of rural bodies shows that “not all residents of all villages were participants in the rural administrative process”, to the exclusion of two stereotypes: “rural settlements in North Bengal during the Gupta period were neither represented by an all-powerful village headman, nor was there an all-inclusive community organization” (p. 44).

It is Chattopadhyaya’s argument that the next phase (sixth and seventh centuries) registers a decline of these rural bodies as well as of the *adhikaraṇas*. The evidence for this and other

associated changes is the following:

- (a) There is a significant contrast in the form of address to the rural bodies, from the earlier *kuśalamanuvarṇya bodhayati* (informs after inquiring about their welfare) to *samādiśati* or *samājñāpayati* (commands or orders) (pp. 44-45).
- (b) The Gunaighar inscription (A.D. 507) shows the decline of both the *adhikaraṇas* and the rural bodies inasmuch as it records: (i) not the sale but an outright gift of land in a village, (ii) communication about which was made not to the village but to officials called *kumārāmātyas*, (iii) and not by an *adhikaraṇa* but by a *mahāsāmanta* named Vijayasena, (iv) who *inter alia* was a *pañcādhikaraṇoparika*, suggesting that he had appropriated the functions of five *adhikaraṇas* (p. 47).
- (c) The villages where land was bought for gift-making no longer “figure in the system of communications” (pp. 49, 51, 53).
- (d) The task of measuring the land for sale is now done by a formal body of officials (*kulavāra*) (pp. 50-51).
- (e) The nature of rural representation changes: *kuṭumbins* disappear as new categories of landholders—*mahāmahattara*, *pradhāna*, *mahāpradhāna*, *agrahārīṇa* and *mahattara-agrahārīṇa*—make their entrance (pp. 48-50, 51-52, 53).
- (f) There is an increase in the importance of the *mahattaras*, who are now represented at the *viśaya* level for the first time, ending the earlier dominance of *prathama-kulika*, *sārthavāha* and so on (pp. 49-50).
- (g) The Mallasarul inscription shows a number of officials at the *bhukti* level in contrast to the Gupta period records, which have only one official at that level (pp. 48, 49). This combines with the presence of the *kulavāras* to bear witness to “increasing bureaucratization” (p. 51).
- (h) The *sāmantas* or “subordinate rulers” appear on the scene, evidenced by the Gunaighar inscription and the Faridpur inscription of the time of Dharmāditya (Regnal year 3) (pp. 47, 49-50).

The simultaneous processes of the decline of the rural bodies and *adhikaraṇas* and the increasing importance of officials corresponded to the shift from the Gupta Empire to regional power centres (p. 129). These were completed in the third phase, by “the early phase of Pāla rule in Bengal in the eighth-ninth century” (p. 53). In place of the *adhikaraṇas*, we now see a large number of officials. As the Khalimpur record of the Pālas shows, “the land transfer documents were no longer concerned with recording various phases” of the purchase and gift of land, but were in the nature of “unilateral, formal administrative decisions which were communicated to official and local residents primarily for the protection of grants” (pp. 53-54).

The presence of officials in large numbers meant the emergence of “another hierarchical pattern” in the rural society, overlying the internal hierarchy of individual villages (p. 54). It also meant the formation of “direct relationship” between “the apex power” and “its rural bases”; the very formation of this relationship, however, probably created a situation of tension between the two by eliminating local community participation in administrative affairs (p. 129).

2.2 The Bengal countryside : An alternative interpretation of the evidence

All of this makes up a formidable intellectual exercise, presented with the intensity of thought and scrupulous care for detail (and parentheses) typical of Chattopadhyaya’s scholarship. For

the most part, however, I happen to see the evidence in a different light.

The first is the composition of *grāmāṣṭakulādhikaraṇa* and *vīthyadhikaraṇa*. They did not consist of officials, who (for example, *āyukta*) are regularly distinguished from them. Accordingly, Chattopadhyaya rightly speaks of “officials who came to appropriate much of the functions of the *adhikaraṇas*” (p. 53, see also p. 46). But he also thinks that these *adhikaraṇas* did not comprise persons from the local communities. The question naturally arises: who did these *adhikaraṇas* then consist of?

The source of the confusion is the detailed lists of the names of *kuṭumbins*, *mahattaras* and others in the Dhanaidaha, Kalaikuri-Sultanpur, Jagdishpur and Mallasarul inscriptions. R.C. Majumdar and R.G. Basak¹⁷ and Yamazaki Toshio¹⁸ thought that *grāmāṣṭakulādhikaraṇa* and *vīthyadhikaraṇa* consisted of these men. There is, in fact, no evidence for this, and Yamazaki, when faced with the very large number of *kuṭumbins* (seventy-six), could equally easily find it “difficult to regard all of them as members of the *adhikaraṇa*”.¹⁹ Chattopadhyaya correctly observes in the case of Kalaikuri-Sultanpur and Jagdishpur inscriptions: “There is nothing to suggest that representatives from these groups constituted the *adhikaraṇa* in the same way in which the *prathama-kulika*, the *prathama-kāyastha*, the *sārthavāha* and the *nagara-śreṣṭhin* were members of the *viṣayādhikaraṇa* of Koṭivārṣa” (p. 40).

At the same time, it is not difficult to understand the supposition of Basak, Yamazaki and others: it was most probably governed by the absence of any detailed reference to the composition of *vīthyadhikaraṇa* and *grāmāṣṭakulādhikaraṇa*, the need to explain the detailed references to the *mahattaras* and others and the definite evidence of the *adhikaraṇa* at Koṭivārṣa *adhikāṣṭhāna* being composed of members from local groups. Indeed, Chattopadhyaya himself is tripped up by the Faridpur inscription of the time of Dharmāditya, Regal year 3. He believes that it refers to the “presence” of *mahattaras* “in the *adhikaraṇa* at the *viṣaya* level” (p.50), whereas these *mahattaras* are distinguished from the *adhikaraṇa*: *adhikaraṇam viṣaya - mahattara - ...*²⁰ - *purogā(h) prakṛtayaśca*.²¹

The only clue to the composition of the two *adhikaraṇas* seems to me to be the two expressions in the Damodarpur copper-plate inscription of the time of Budhagupta, Gupta year 163: *mahattarādyāṣṭakulādhikaraṇam grāmikakuṭumbinaśca* and *mahattarādyadhikaraṇakuṭumbibhiḥ*.²² Following Basak,²³ Chattopadhyaya takes these to mean “*mahattaras*, the *aṣṭakulādhikaraṇa*, the *grāmika* and the *kuṭumbins*” and “*mahattaras* and others, officers and householders” respectively (pp. 37-38). Accordingly, he finds the *mahattaras* and others “associated” with the *adhikaraṇa* (p. 38), not constituting it. However, the term *ādi* does not seem to mean “and others” here, for the others are specified in the same *pada* as *kuṭumbins*, *grāmikas* and so on; in the compound *mahattarādyadhikaraṇakuṭumbibhiḥ*, one may ask, why should *kuṭumbins* be

¹⁷ Chapter X, “Administration”, in R.C. Majumdar, ed, *History of Bengal*, Vol. I, reprint (N.V. Publications, Patna, 1971), p. 269.

¹⁸ “Some Aspects of Land-sale Inscriptions in Fifth and Sixth Century Bengal”, *Acta Asiatica*, No. 42 (August 1982), pp. 29, 33-34.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 29.

²⁰ Here the personal names of the *mahattaras* are given.

²¹ D.C. Sircar, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, 2nd edn (University of Calcutta, Calcutta, 1965), p. 364, ll. 4-6.

²² *Ibid.*, pp. 333-34, ll. 2-3, 10.

²³ *Geographia Indica*, Vol. XV (1919-20), p. 137.

mentioned, if “others” are already denoted by “*ādi*”? *Ādi* most likely meant here “headed by”. As such, the two expressions translate better as “the *aṣṭakulādhikaraṇa* headed by the *mahattaras*, and the *kuṭumbins* who are *grāmikas*” and “by the *kuṭumbins* of the *adhikaraṇa* headed by the *mahattaras*” respectively: this is how D.R. Bhandarkar and D.C. Sircar routinely understood them.²⁴

So the village notables were inducted into the polity in discrete groups to form supra-village administrative bodies called *grāmāṣṭakulādhikaraṇa* or *vīthyadhikaraṇa*. These *adhikaraṇas* were thus organized on the same lines as their urban counterpart, the *adhiṣṭhānādhikaraṇa* of Koṭivarṣa *viṣaya*, which is known to have consisted of the representatives of various urban groups.²⁵

It remains to explain the reference to a number of villagers by name in the Dhanaidaha and other inscriptions. It has been linked with the theory of popular voice in the local administration, at which we must now take a critical look. First, not *all* the records in any period refer to them, while the records mentioning them are dispersed over the Gupta and post-Gupta periods: we do not have the lists of individual names, for instance, in the Damodarpur copper-plate inscription of the time of Budhagupta (Gupta year 163), Baigram inscription of the Gupta year 128 and Paharpur inscription of the Gupta year 152. Second, it is not true to say that only in the late Gupta and post-Gupta inscriptions the villages where land was purchased do not figure in the system of communications. Even earlier, the two Damodarpur inscriptions of the time of Kumāragupta I and one of the time of Budhagupta, relating to Koṭivarṣa *viṣaya*, do not refer at all to the villagers. And we cannot be sure that the late Gupta Gunaighar inscription refers only to officials and not to the villagers (p. 47). As Sircar noted, about eight *akṣaras* in the line describing the addresses are lost and “may be restored as *brāhmaṇādīnkuṭumbinaḥ* or *samavetānkuṭumbinaḥ*.”²⁶ Third, it was not land itself that was being sold, but the right to cultivate it free of taxes, as Kosambi always stressed.²⁷ So when the king decided to make a grant himself, as in the case of the Gunaighar inscription, it had to be an “outright gift”, there being no question of any procedure of sale. The point is made in the record itself that such a gift brought loss to the king, who is said to have courted (financial) pinch in the process.²⁸ The comparison with the Khalimpur record of the Pālas is even less helpful. It was concerned with the gift of state revenues from settled areas and not of revenue-free land, and we should not expect to find there details of sale of land. Fourth, the exemption of the gift land from all revenue obligations would also explain the provision that it was not to be so located as to disturb people’s own cultivation. It was the king’s *right* to demand proper cultivation of land to ensure his proper income from

24 *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. III, revised edn (Archaeological Survey of India, New Delhi, 1981), pp. 337, 338; D.C. Sircar, *Indian Epigraphical Glossary* (Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1966), p. 191; cf. Yamazaki, *op.cit.*, p. 28.

25 The reference is to the *adhiṣṭhānādhikaraṇa* of Koṭivarṣa-*viṣaya*, and not to the *viṣayādhikaraṇa* of Koṭivarṣa as Chattohadhyaya supposes, following Basak again (*EI*, Vol. XXI). The comparisons with the Pañcanagarī *viṣayādhikaraṇa* and the Vārakamaṇḍala *viṣayādhikaraṇa* (pp. 38, 49-50) do not, therefore, seem to be appropriate.

26 *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 341, ll.2 and n.5.

27 For example, *An Introduction to the Study of Indian History*, 2nd edn (Popular Prakashan, Bombay, 1975), pp. 320-21.

28 *pīḍāmapyūrikṛtya*, Sircar, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 342, ll. 9-10. The reference to this pecuniary loss should put paid to Sircar’s oft-repeated belief that in such cases the real donor was not the king but the persons who requested the king to make the grant and who must have paid the king for this.

it, and so the provision was aimed more to safeguard royal income from the tax-paying fields than to accommodate rural landed interests. Fifth, the contrasts in the forms of address to the people do not really tell us much about their importance in the polity. Sharma saw in the expression *matamastu* in the early Pāla charters a formal recognition of the people's rights formerly enjoyed, and its substitution by *viditamastu* in later Pāla charters indicated to him the abandoning of even the formal recognition.²⁹ Chattopadhyaya, who does not note this concern of Sharma, sees a similar implication in the contrast between *bodhayati* and *samādiśati/samājñāpayati*. These logical inferences, however, find no further support in the records. None of the pre-Pāla land-sale charters in Bengal, which furnish the lists of the names of individuals and which Sharma considered as signifying popular say in the government,³⁰ has the form *matamastu* while some of them have the term *viditam*.³¹ In the Paschimbhag and the three Mainamati inscriptions the contrasting forms occur together: *mānayati bodhayati samājñāpayati/samādiśati*,³² as they do in the Khalimpur record (p. 54, l.10).

What, then, can be the significance of the irregular and chronologically dispersed references to the village notables by name and/or the villagers in general? My submission is that these are best understood in the context of the provisions for land transfer in the *śāstras*. The law digests lay down that village elders, neighbours, kinsmen and so on were to be present at the transfer of title and the delimiting of the land. The *Mitākṣarā* (on *Yājñavalkya*, II.114) explains that the consent of these persons was desirable but not obligatory. It was desired for making public the transaction, not that the transaction would be invalid without the consent of the village.³³ The law digests also prescribe the demarcation of the boundaries in various ways to foreclose the possibilities of land disputes (*sīmāvivāda*),³⁴ and this injunction too is followed in most—though not all—charters.³⁵

What seems to have been thought indispensable was administrative procedure, which was common to all the records. In each case—whether the villagers were informed or not, whether the boundaries were described or not—the record-keepers (*pustapālas*) ascertained through investigation (*avadhāraṇayā avadhṛtam*) that the details about the land, the rate of purchase and the like were correct. Only then the transaction occurred. The Dhanaidaha and the Mallasarul inscriptions refer to the details having been ascertained and in order (*avasthāpya, avadhṛtam, amakramah*) without specifying the personnel who did that. The *pustapālas* are not mentioned

²⁹ *Indian Feudalism*, pp. 93-94, 182 and n. 1.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, pp. 93, 113-14.

³¹ Sircar, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 352, l.2 (Kalaikuri-Sultanpur); *idem*, *Epigraphic Discoveries*, p. 61, l.3.

³² *Epigraphic Discoveries*, p. 67, ll.33-34; p. 74, l.50; p. 76, ll. 16-17; p. 80, l.42.

³³ *vivahāraprakāśanārthamevāpekṣyate na punargrāmānumatyā vinā vyavahārasiddhiḥ*, P.V. Kane, *History of Dharmaśāstra*, Vol. III, 2nd edn (Poona, 1973), p. 479 and n. 882.

The non-obligatory nature of the need to record the names of the villagers could be used to explain the differences between the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur and the Jagdishpur inscriptions in this respect. However, this need not be invoked and the differences noted by Chattopadhyaya (pp. 40-41) may be understood thus: the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur inscription has a much bigger list of *mahattaras* and *kuṭumbins* probably because of the involvement of a larger number of villages; the seven *kāyasthas* were among the donors in this record; and the *pustapālas* and the *kuḷika* do appear in the Jagdishpur record also and have been missed by the author through oversight.

³⁴ Kane, *op.cit.*, Vol.III, pp. 502-3.

³⁵ See in particular the convergence of the Baigram inscription, l.19 (Sircar, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 358), and *Māta*, VIII, 250-51.

in this role even in the Gunaighar inscription. There the king himself was the donor, and nothing could have been odder than his rescript being verified by his officials. But the fact that he could donate eleven *pāṭakas* of *khila* land in five plots, each demarcated precisely, without going to the village shows that the *pustapālas* had supplied the information prior³⁶ to his making the grant. A relevant administrative procedure is duly transcribed: the names of the persons involved in the transmission and execution of the royal order are spelt out, thus fixing the responsibility.

This brings us to the other nuances which we must introduce in Chattopadhyaya's narrative. While his point about the substantial increase in the number of officials³⁶ remains with all its significance for the hierarchy in rural society there were more officials in the pre-Pāla period than he supposes and there was direct contact between the king and the villagers then too through his officials, which he denies. Below the *āyuktaka* and the *kumārāmātya* officials such as the *pustapālas*, *sthāyīpālas* and *kulikas*³⁷ are known to have functioned; together they were called (*saṃ*) *vyavahārins*. Second, the designation *pañcādhikaraṇoparika* in the Gunaighar inscription should suggest a functionary who supervised and controlled five *adhikaraṇas* as an *uparika*³⁸ and not one who appropriated their functions; moreover, it is not necessary that these *adhikaraṇas* were the same as those under discussion, given the variety of *adhikaraṇas* in the Gupta polity.³⁹ Third, while the local notables ceased to function as a corporate official body (*adhikarana*), some of them continued to be inducted in the administration as individuals, so much so that U.N. Ghoshal could at times think that *mahattaras* were "not private individuals" but "administrative agents".⁴⁰ Fourth, the multiple designations of Vijayasena in the Gunaighar inscription (*mahāpratihāra*, *mahāpīlupati*, *pañcādhikaraṇoparika*, etc.) underscore the point that the increase in the number of designations may not indicate a *proportionate* increase in the number of officials. The last comment relates to the significance of the term *sāmanta*, but this is to anticipate the discussion in a later section.

2.3 The village as a part of the state society

Chattopadhyaya brings out several other ways in which the villages formed "integral components of the state structure" (pp. 128-29). The hierarchies among the rural settlements were mainly administrative/political: *Palāśavṛndaka* being different from *Caṇḍagrāma* (pp. 37-38), there being different nodes in the *Cāhamāna* polity (pp. 77-83), and *Kalikaṭṭi* being the "foremost" village of *Magare nāḍu*, with a record office and a set of officials (pp. 102, 126). The political decisions from above significantly altered the character of individual villages (clubbing together several villages in a single network of surplus distribution through a royal grant, the settlement of *brāhmaṇas* and other religious and political grantees, and so on).

To what extent a political decision about a village, determining its status in relation to the neighbouring villages, was influenced by its location or social make-up remains elusive for lack

36 Cf. D.D. Kosambi, *An Introduction to the Study of Indian History*, p. 321.

37 The *kulika* Bhima in the Jagdishpur plate who collected money from the purchasers of land was obviously the official in charge of ten villages, called *daśagrāmika* elsewhere, who was entitled to one *kula* of land as salary. see P.V. Kane, *op.cit.*, Vol. III, pp. 150, 980.

38 Cf. *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 343, n.5.

39 *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. III, p. 286, n.7.

40 U.N. Ghoshal, *Contributions to the History of the Hindu Revenue System*, 2nd edn (Saraswat Library, Calcutta, 1972), pp. 270-71; cf. Romila Thapar, *The Past and Prejudice* (National Book Trust, New Delhi, 1975), p. 37.

of necessary information and the tilt of the sources towards “things political” (p. 126). The changing history of Kalikaṭṭi as documented by the author is explicable largely in terms of political initiative from above, as he duly notes (pp. 114, 129-30). But we are also told: “Hoysaḷa royal measures with regard to the village were responses to what was happening in the village at different points of time” (p. 93). This appears to contradict the burden of the narrative and the author’s other statements, but it may only modify them for a thesis of reciprocal influence or correspondence. However, just what this relation between outside interference and internal dynamic was will have to be elaborated, probably with the help of additional data at the author’s disposal. For Bengal the political geography of Palāśavṛndaka and Caṇḍagrāma villages (pp. 37-38) would seem to correspond to their social geography as reconstructed below (section 3.2).

2.4 The state and the distribution of landed property: Need for rethinking

Chattopadhyaya emphasizes at many places the ways in which he departs from the dominant methods, concerns and theses of the current historiography. There are yet more ways in which the data supplied by him can be used to make a critical intervention. The first is the relation of the state to the distribution of landed property. The records of the Cāhamānas of Naḍḍula refer to the grants of land/land revenue to the state personnel. Each record gives the impression of the creation of a hereditary assignment. To take the Nadol plates of 1161, for instance, one could only agree with Sharma’s understanding of it: “A very clear grant to a royal scion is found in the Nadol plates of 1161, according to which twelve villages with absolute rights were assigned ... to the *rājaputra* Kirtipāla. This fief was assigned to Kirtipāla in perpetuity, for when he makes over a yearly sum of two *drammas* from each of the twelve villages to a Jain temple he asks his descendants to observe the terms of his grant”.⁴¹ Likewise, B.N.S. Yadava spoke of the generally life-time tenures of secular grants on the basis of the *Lekhapaddhati* and the *Kathākośa* and drew the contrast with the system in the Naḍḍula Cāhamāna polity: “However, some records, as those of the Cāhamānas of Naḍḍula, indicate that the assignments to the members of the royal clan were *permanent* and *hereditary*”.⁴² In his paper on the Rajputs, Chattopadhyaya himself sees assignments in the Naḍḍula Cāhamāna polity as the evidence for “the distribution of land among the royal kinsmen”, which was one of the “certain new features of land distribution and territorial system” associated with the emergence of early Rajputs.⁴³

All of this may now safely be abandoned. By focusing on a village and a group of villages Chattopadhyaya describes how the assignments “often changed hands” (p. 85). “The fact” does not signify much to him beyond “the existence of some kind of pressure” (ibid.). In fact, the evidence marshalled by him points to frequent *transfers* of assignments, which clearly prevented their conversion into hereditary property, foreshadowing the latter-day *iqṭā’* system. That the phraseology of the above-mentioned Nadol grant was merely stylized may be seen in the facts that ten years later, Sonāṇā, one of the villages granted to Kirtipāla in 1161, was the benefice

⁴¹ *Indian Feudalism*, p. 144. More precisely, Kirtipāla requests any such person as might come after the termination of his own *vamśa* not to resume the grant (*EI*, Vol. IX, 9B, v.9). Apart from this, the term for perpetuity was *candārakkakṣitīkālam yāvat* (ibid., l. 26).

⁴² *Society and Culture in Northern India in the Twelfth Century* (Central Book Depot, Allahabad, 1973), p. 147 (emphases added).

⁴³ “Origin of the Rajputs: The Political, Economic and Social Processes in Early Medieval Rajasthan”, *The Indian Historical Review*, Vol. III, No. 1 (July 1976), pp. 71-72.

of *ṭhakkura* Anasiha in 1171, and five years later, of princes Lāṣanapāla and Abhayapāla (p. 85).

These data also disprove the existence of the “small principality of the Guhilas” in the kingdom of the Naḍḍula Cāhamānas that we had so far supposed⁴⁴ on the basis of three records mentioning Guhila *ṭhakkura* Rājadeva. Yadava naturally called him a vassal of the Cāhamāna Rāyapāla.⁴⁵ In fact, Naḍḍulai was a temporary assignment of Rājadeva, held before him by the princes Rudrapāla and Amṛtapāla and after him the assignment was probably split, a part of which passed first to Anasiha and later to princes Lāṣanapāla and Abhayapāla (pp. 84-85).

The system of the transfer of assignments is also borne out by the history of Kalikaṭṭi, where Chattopadhyaya describes a succession of *sāmantas* who were brought from outside and given Kalikaṭṭi “free from all impediments” (pp. 94, 101). These *sāmantas* were not local magnates but were transferred to Kalikaṭṭi from the other parts of the Hoysaḷa kingdom (pp. 102-5); later on the assignment was transferred to the queen Umādevī (p. 108). The case of *sāmanta* Goyideva (p. 102) shows that it was not even a life tenure.

Chattopadhyaya is thus quite right in insisting that the succession of *sāmantas* did not “lead to the emergence of a permanent base of *sāmanta* or feudatory control in the village” (p. 101). But the denial is only for Kalikaṭṭi. The very title of *sāmanta* means to him—as it does to others—that the persons being called *sāmantas* were hereditary lords and so of a different order than the officials. Thus for polity in early medieval Bengal, he duly notes “the emergence of the *sāmanta* stratum” (p. 47). And although he can occasionally speak of “a permanent base of *sāmanta* or feudatory control”, in general he has reservations about calling *sāmantas* “feudatories” and prefers the term “subordinate rulers”, apparently after Sircar. One usage seems no happier than the other, however.

To call the Kalikaṭṭi *sāmantas* “rulers” is to run counter to the fact that they were royal appointees, exercising delegated authority. They were *rājapurūṣas*, and the contrast Chattopadhyaya drew in his presidential address to the Indian History Congress—between rule through *sāmantas* and rule through *rājapurūṣas*—does not seem applicable here.⁴⁶

Sāmanta regularly means the holder of a military rank in Sanskrit literature, of which simply no note has been taken in the discussions of the term by the historians of early medieval India (Kosambi, Lallanji Gopal, Sharma, Yadava, etc.). *Sāmanta* very probably denotes a military rank here. Chattopadhyaya states: “The composition of the subordinate rulers [that is, the *sāmantas*]... suggests that they came either from families with local bases or from those which had already attained a high military/administrative rank” (p. 102). In fact, six out of the seven *sāmantas* during Hoysaḷa rule (p. 119) had known military background/association (pp. 95, 102-3) with no hint of any territorial lordship. This would also apply to the reference in pre-Hoysaḷa Karnataka to *sāmanta* Śrī Muttara, who was in charge of Āsandi *nāḍu* and was given two villages (Kalikaṭṭi and an adjoining one) as *vṛtti* on his death in a battle (pp. 93-94). Obviously he did not control the *nāḍu* as its hereditary lord nor any other area, for then his family would not have needed the two villages as *vṛtti* (source of livelihood).

44 H.C. Ray, *The Dynastic History of Northern India*, Vol. II, 2nd edn (Munshiram Manoharlal, New Delhi, 1973), pp. 1203-4.

45 Op.cit., p. 150.

46 “Political Processes and Structure of Polity in Early Medieval India” in his *The Making of Early Medieval India*, p. 217.

For only one of these *sāmantas*, Goyideva, there is a *prima facie* case for his family having a local base: in a Kalikaṭṭi record he is called *huliyerupuravarādhīśvara*; “in 1139 his eldest brother *mahāsāmanta* Ceṭṭaya was ruling Huliyeṛu”; and “in 1148 when *sāmanta* Goyideva was no longer ruling Kalikaṭṭi, he is found ruling Huliyeṛu-12 as a *mahāsāmanta*” (p. 102). Even if these pieces of evidence are taken to suggest the territorial lordship of the family over Huliyeṛu, there is nothing to indicate that the title of *sāmanta* was held by virtue of the lordship. And the following considerations would show that the above evidence could simply describe Goyideva and his brother as administering Huliyeṛu as officials and not as its hereditary lords: (i) Kalikaṭṭi was administered by three generations of *sāmantas* in succession (p. 103) and we know that they were not its hereditary lords; and (ii) *sāmanta* Siṅgarasa enjoyed Kalikaṭṭi as his benefice while administering Kunigilu-*nāḍ* (pp. 94-95). So the reference to Goyideva as *huliyerupuravarādhīśvara* in a Kalikaṭṭi record could depict a similar situation: Huliyeṛu was his administrative charge and Kalikaṭṭi his benefice.

It seems also clear that Kalikaṭṭi was given to these *sāmantas* mainly as their revenue assignment. This is suggested by the term *sarva-bādhā-parihāra*,⁴⁷ the unfeasibility of confining the duties of such important functionaries to the administration of one village only and the facts that while Ballanna is known to have been in charge of the entire Magare *nāḍu* of which Kalikaṭṭi was a part (p. 103), Siṅgarasa was in charge of Kunigilu-*nāḍ* (p. 95). If this were so and if *sāmanta* denoted a military rank how justified is it to refer to them as “*sāmantas of Kalikaṭṭi*”? Going by Appendix 1 of the fourth chapter (p. 119), *sāmanta* occurs as the title of these persons with no explicit association with any functional or territorial charge; till that is established, it may be no more valid to speak of *mahāsāmanta* Siṅgarasa as *mahāsāmanta of Kalikaṭṭi* than to speak of *mahāpradhāna senādhipati hiriya heggaḍe* Ballanna as *mahāpradhāna/senādhipati/hiriya heggaḍe of Kalikaṭṭi*. To call them *sāmantas of Kalikaṭṭi* is also to narrow the geographical scope of the office to a village, which becomes questionable in view of their controlling entire *nāḍus* (while villagers may have their king, he is not called “the king of a village”).

For Bengal too, we would need independent evidence (and not inference from title alone) to be certain that there was an “emergence of the *sāmanta stratum*” (pp. 47, 49). The expression *śudūparilikhitakāgamasāmantarājabhiḥ* (improved reading: *likhitakāgāma* and restoration: *likhitamāgāmi*)⁴⁸ in the aforementioned Faridpur inscription does not refer to feudatories/subordinate kings, as Sircar⁴⁹ and Chattopadhyaya (pp. 50, 60-61 n. 58) believe. The terms are *sāmanta* and *rājan*, and not *sāmantarāja*, for then the declension would have been *sāmantarājaiḥ* and not *sāmantarājabhiḥ*. So F.E. Pargiter was more faithful to the text in rendering the term as “neighbouring kings”. However, keeping the context as well as the text in mind, I feel tempted to see here a reference to the future (*āgāmi*) neighbouring cultivators (*sāmantas*) and kings (*rājans*) being requested to honour the land transactions. The Dharmasāstras regularly mention *sāmantas* in this sense in this context.⁵⁰

The foregoing ought to make us take a new look at the evidence for “political feudalism” in

⁴⁷ Sircar, *Indian Epigraphical Glossary*, q.v. *parihāra*, *sarva-bādhā-parihāra*, *sarva-pīḍā-parihṛta*, *parihṛta-sarva-pīḍā*, etc.

⁴⁸ *Idem*, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 366, l.20 and n. 13.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, n. 14.

⁵⁰ Kane, *op.cit.*; R.S. Sharma, *Indian Feudalism*, p. 166.

early medieval India, which has generally not been questioned by the historians critical of the feudalism model. Sircar's understanding of the political processes in early medieval India⁵¹ is uncannily similar to Sharma's. Chattopadhyaya finds "no reason to dispute the empirical validity of" "the *sāmanta*—feudatory system... (as) the hallmark of the structure of polity in early medieval India".⁵² Nor does H. Kulke⁵³ or Irfan Habib.⁵⁴ Harbans Mukhia finds himself in full agreement with Sharma and others on this issue. If one were to understand West European feudalism in political and legal terms (as Perry Anderson does), Mukhia states, "pre-thirteenth century early medieval India... can find herself comfortably placed there [that is, in the category of feudalism]..."⁵⁵

3 Society

A brāhmaṇa-centred view of early medieval socio-economic structure has been the dominant orthodoxy among the historians, whether it is brāhmaṇa-peasant polarization version of Indian Feudalism model or the brāhmaṇa-peasant alliance version of the Segmentary State model. The brāhmaṇa-peasant dichotomy also assumes a lack of differentiation among the peasantry. The Indian Feudalism model places an almost exclusive emphasis on the landgrants as the mechanism for introducing the brāhmaṇas in the countryside as "key actors" in the major historical processes (p. 127), creating the "brāhmaṇa-peasant dichotomy... from above" (p. 10). Chattopadhyaya seeks to offer an altogether different version.

3.1 Did the brāhmaṇas come before or with the landgrants?

Thus "even in the early Gupta period, the brāhmaṇas were *already* a major landholding group in north Bengal" (p. 42, emphases added). This statement is based on the references to individual brāhmaṇa landholders and such expressions as *brāhmaṇāḍīṅgrāmakuṭumbinaḥ* in the inscriptions (pp. 42-43). We may in addition draw attention to the very important evidence of the Paschimbhag inscription where brāhmaṇas figure as a group among the tax-paying peasantry.⁵⁶ However, lest we should think that brāhmaṇas were everywhere present before the landgrants, a contrast needs to be drawn with the evidence from Kalikaṭṭi where the "the brāhmaṇas do not

51 *Landlordism and Tenancy in Ancient and Medieval India as Revealed by Epigraphical Records* (Lucknow, 1969), pp. 6-7.

52 "Political Processes", op.cit., pp. 194, 195.

53 H. Kulke and D. Rothermund, *A History of India* (Barnes and Noble Books, Totowa, 1986), pp. 127-36; cf. B. Stein, *Peasant State and Society in Medieval South India* (Oxford University Press, Delhi, 1980), pp. 47-48, 70. Elsewhere Stein denies the existence of fief only in medieval south India ("The State and the Agrarian Order in Medieval South India: A Historiographical Critique", in B. Stein, ed, *Essays on South India* (University of Hawaii Press, Hawaii, 1975), p. 85.

54 I. Habib, "Classifying Pre-colonial India", in T.J. Byres and H. Mukhia, ed, *Feudalism and Non-European Societies* (Frank Cass, London, 1995), p. 50.

55 "Was There Feudalism in Indian History?", in Byres and Mukhia, ed, op.cit., p. 278, n. 15. The tenor of Mukhia's piece, however, has tended to generate a different impression. See B. Stein, "The Segmentary State: Interim Reflections", in H. Kulke, ed, *The State in India, 1000-1700* (Oxford University Press, Delhi, 1995), p. 143: "... Harbans Mukhia, who has attacked the feudalism formulation from the point of view of its economic as well as political claims ...".

56 Sircar, *Epigraphic Discoveries*, p. 68, ll. 56-57.

at all figure prominently before its conversion as an *agrahāra*" (p. 127),⁵⁷ that is, before A.D. 1215 (p. 110). I do not draw this contrast to raise a polemic over the importance of the mechanism of landgrants but to urge a more careful scrutiny of the evidence and to argue that the issue before us is not a matter of theoretical supposition but of actual historical demonstration. Drawing a balance sheet would, therefore, be premature at this stage when the other type of investigation has just begun.

3.2 Patterns of stratification other than landgrant-induced ones

By systematizing the various strands of his thought, we can see five ways in which Chattopadhyaya's narrative differs from the one dominated by *brāhmaṇa*-peasant/*śhakkura*-peasant dichotomy: differentiation among the peasantry represented by various "non-*brāhmaṇa*" groups; juxtaposition (and not contradistinction) of *brāhmaṇa agraḥārīṇas* with other categories of landholders into a composite group for certain important purposes; hierarchy among the villages in terms of their having or lacking in prominent landholders; the presence of officials in substantial numbers forming a supra-village hierarchical pattern, and; differentiation among the *brāhmaṇas* and its complex interlocking with differentiation among the other *jāti* groups as seen in the Paschimbhag plates.

A good starting-point for the first issue is the statement from the concluding chapter:

The Gupta inscriptions already show us that the important segments of the rural society were the *kuṭumbins* and the *mahattaras* who could be distinguished from other residents and that with the passage of time further hierarchical groupings of non-*brāhmaṇa* rural residents are suggested by such categories as *mahāmahattaras* and *mahāpradhāna*. In south Karnataka too a somewhat similar pattern is suggested by the distinction among different *gāvunḍa* groups, by the presence of the *nāyakas* and of other categories, including the *sāmantas*, which would make the structure of its village society much more complex than simple polarisation. What needs to be noted in particular is that the process of the emergence of these categories does not precede the rise in status of the *brāhmaṇas* as recipients of land or the proliferation of *brāhmaṇa*-dominated rural settlements; both are simultaneous processes (p. 128).

Two minor objections may be dealt with quickly. First, *mahattaras*, *kuṭumbins*, *mahāmahattaras*, etc., were not "non-*brāhmaṇa* rural residents"; they included *brāhmaṇas* too (pp. 42-43, 48, 51-52, 56). These were thus *varṇa/jāti*-neutral categories. Second, while the emergence of *mahāmahattara*, *mahāpradhāna* and so on was simultaneous with that of the *brāhmaṇa* grantees, the emergence of other categories—*mahattaras* and *kuṭumbins* in Bengal and *gāvunḍa* groups and others in Kalikaṭṭi—definitely preceded the rise in status of the *brāhmaṇa* recipients of land, although in Bengal both come into *our* view simultaneously.

The terms *mahattara* and *kuṭumbin* have been variously understood by the experts such as Bangtser, Sircar and Yamazaki and so merit a detailed discussion. The sources do not tell us *how*

⁵⁷ Paradoxically, the sentence occurs in the context of the criticism of the belief that "landgrants hold the key to understanding the historical processes in operation" (p. 127). Since Chattopadhyaya's criticisms have been directed not to repair the Indian Feudalism or other constructs, nor even to assess them in terms of the pros and cons, but to underline the need for another, more satisfying construct, he has not been concerned to note the ways in which his data could be used to buttress some of the generalizations in the extant constructs.

the *mahattaras* differed from the *kuṭumbins*, and both from the rest of the population. Drawing on Sircar's comparison of the names in the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur and Jagdishpur inscriptions, Chattopadhyaya notes that "individuals... listed previously in the category of *vīthi-mahattaras* figured, eight years later, as only *kuṭumbins*" (p. 43). Sircar sought to explain this change in status from *mahattara* to *kuṭumbin* by postulating a system of elected representatives, in which people could fail to be elected to the same position, and the failure would be reflected in the changing status. This has been effectively rebutted by Chattopadhyaya (ibid.), but he does not explain the "changes in status of some *vīthi-mahattaras*" (ibid.).

Actually the fact does not seem to exist. Sircar spoke of the change in status of only *one* person—*mahattara* Umayāśas figuring later as *kuṭumbin* Umayāśas—and not of "some individuals". The two inscriptions do not give the parentage, *jāti* or *gotra* associations of the persons (which we have in many records from other areas), but simply provide their proper names and status as *mahattara*, *kuṭumbin*, *pustapāla* and so on. The identity of the proper name and the status help us to infer that *kulika* Bhima of one record was the same as *kulika* Bhīma of the other, as were the four *mahattaras* and two *pustapālas*. Some *kuṭumbins* from the two inscriptions may also be identified with each other:⁵⁸ Śiva, another (*apara*) Śiva,⁵⁹ Śivakuṇḍa, Rudra, Bhava, Guha, Naradeva, Hariśarmman, Sarpapālita, etc.

Now, the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur inscription refers to a *mahattara* Umayāśas and the Jagdishpur inscription to a *kuṭumbin* Umayāśas. This can be taken to mean either that Umayāśas who was a *mahattara* became a *kuṭumbin* later or that a *mahattara* of the first record had the same name as a *kuṭumbin* of the other. The latter option—that they were different persons—seems the more probable one. One reason is: proper names alone, if they are in conflict with the corresponding statuses, do not seem a secure basis for identification. On the one hand, there are a number of common names in each record: two Yaśoviṣṇus, two Bhavanāthas, two Jayaviṣṇus,⁶⁰ two Guhaviṣṇus and two Śivas in the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur inscription, and two Śivas in the Jagdishpur inscription. We cannot know which Yaśoviṣṇu of the first record is to be identified with the Yaśoviṣṇu of the second. On the other hand, there is one person common to both the records but whose name does not figure as completely alike. This is Acyutadāsa, the *āyuktaka* in Kalaikuri-Sultanpur record; apparently he was the same as *āyuktaka* Acyuta of the Jagdishpur

58 Sircar's listing of the names of *kuṭumbins* common to both the records is faulty, omitting many names that are common (for example, Yaśoviṣṇu, Śivakuṇḍa, Rudra, Bhava, etc.) and including names that are not common (Kumārayāśas, Satyaviṣṇu, Bhavanāga), *Epigraphic Discoveries*, p. 10. Chattopadhyaya's list of the names in the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur record, prepared from N.B. Sanyal's edited text, does not tally exactly with the names in Sircar's text.

59 The expression *śivāparaśiva* is common to both the records. For the Jagdishpur record, Sircar takes it to mean two persons—Śiva and the second (*apara*) Śiva—and identifies them with the two men in the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur record, ibid. He does not give reasons why *apara* was not a part of the proper name, the other person being called *Aparaśiva*, which is Chattopadhyaya's understanding for the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur inscription (p. 65). There are a number of cases in the two records of two men having the same name, but *apara* is never used to qualify the second man. This may be an objection to Sircar's rendering. It is surmounted by the fact that the rules of *sandhi* are not observed in these two records for proper names (and there were numerous occasions for this in the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur record and at least one in the Jagdishpur record), so that the use of *sandhi* in *śivāparaśiva* would suggest that *apara* was used in its literal sense and not as a part of the proper name. In that case, however, line 6 of Sircar's transcript will have to be emended where he takes *vasuśiva* to mean one name, while they would be two separate names—Vasu and Śiva (*Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 353).

60 Not in Sircar's transcript.

plate. But if we insist too much on the complete identity of proper names and prefer it to the status association, we shall have to suppose that *kuṭumbin* Acyuta of the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur record became the high official *āyuktaka* Acyuta of the Jagdishpur plate about eight years later. But once we see that *āyuktaka* Acyuta was the same as *āyuktaka* Acyuta we face further problems with the comparison on the basis of names only: Kumāra of Kalaikuri-Sultanpur record could very well be Kumārayaśas or Kumārabhūti of the Jagdishpur record; Acyuta of the latter was not necessarily *kuṭumbin* Acyuta of the former, for he could as well be *kuṭumbin* Acyutabhadrā, and so on. The second reason is: we cannot be certain that there was no *kuṭumbin* Umayāśas in the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur inscription, who could be identified with his namesake in the other record. There is a *kuṭumbin* in the former (p. 65, no. 47) whose name begins with "Uma" and becomes illegible thereafter; it is possible that the name was Umayāśas.

Mahattaras have often been seen as "village elders", but this does not seem applicable in our case, for who would then be *mahāmahattaras*? The later disappearance of *kuṭumbins* and the prominence of *mahattaras* is simply incomprehensible in terms of the growing importance of older elements at the cost of younger ones. The proportion of *mahattaras* to *kuṭumbins* in the Kalaikuri-Sultanpur and the Jagdishpur records is 7:78/76 and 4:28 respectively; taking them as random samples and *mahattaras* as elders, we shall have an outstanding rate of mortality among the elders in early medieval India or the more outstanding spectacle of doddering old men leading the village and assisting the state personnel.⁶¹ Finally, the Paschimbhag inscription describes the allotment of land in different quantities to Vedic brāhmaṇas, maidservants, florists and others including *mahattara* brāhmaṇas; *mahattara* must mean here something different from "elder".

All of this leaves us with the interpretation of *mahattara* as substantial landowners. This would be supported by the comparable influence wielded by such landowners in contemporary India. Yamazaki thought that economic criterion did not distinguish *kuṭumbins* from *mahattaras* as the Baigram inscription refers to two *kuṭumbin* brothers donating 3.25 *kulyavāpas* of land to a temple built by their father; so these brothers "must have belonged to the wealthy class in the village", yet "they were not given the title of *mahattara*".⁶² However, the fact that some *kuṭumbins* were rich peasants may simply show that other *kuṭumbins* were men of lesser means, rather than the absence of any economic distinction between *kuṭumbins* and *mahattaras*, who could be still bigger landowners. This would be supported by the distinction between the terms *pradhāna-kuṭumbins* and *kṣudraprakṛti-kuṭumbins* that we see in the inscriptions,⁶³ the

61. As Pargiter showed, two persons Anācāra and Ghoṣacandra figured as *mahattaras* in each of the two Faridpur charters separated by at least twenty years and so were likely to have been "quite young men" when they were first called *mahattaras* (*The Indian Antiquary*, Vol. XXXIX, 1910, p. 213; Yamazaki, *op.cit.*, p. 27). Pargiter used this to argue that some individuals could be *mahattaras* by virtue of their wealth without reference to their age. He thought that others became *mahattaras* "by ability and age" on the following ground: "A man born to position is not ordinarily known by his son's name, so that Arjuna-bappa, 'Arjuna's father' in plate A [that is, Faridpur charter of the time of Dharmāditya, Regnal year 3], had probably reached his position by age" (*loc. cit.*). However, this ought to mean that Arjuna-bappa was so old that he could no longer be recognized by his own name and that Arjuna was known better than his father, which hardly goes with the importance of the *mahattara*. And it is more likely that Arjuna and Bappa were two names, Bappa having been a fairly common personal name (Sircar, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 364, n. 4).

62. Yamazaki, *op.cit.*, p. 27.

63. Sircar, *Select Inscriptions*, Vol. I, p. 333, l.3; Sircar, *Epigraphic Discoveries*, p. 61, l.2.

proportion between *mahattaras* and *kuṭumbins* noted above, the testimony of the contemporary text *Niśīthacūrṇi* that *mahattaras* were the foremost persons in the villages in terms of wealth, birth and so on,⁶⁴ and the reference in the tenth-century *Bṛhathkathākośa* to a *mahattara* who could occupy the pasture near a village by giving one thousand pitchers of ghee to the king.⁶⁵ We thus probably have two strata among the big landowners—*kuṭumbins* and *mahattaras*—to which a third stratum of *mahāmahattara* was added later in some places. These categories were not just lexical, but operational: living beings differentiated themselves and were recognized as such in the state records. But we know practically nothing about their socio-economic status beyond the fact of the differentiation, that is, about the size of their holdings or such privileges as they may have received from the state. This lack of information has a significant bearing on the historiographical treatment of these categories.

We may also perhaps doubt if the categories of *pradhāna* and *mahāpradhāna*, mentioned in the Egra copper-plate, denoted social divisions (pp. 51-52, 53, 128). The acceptance of these terms in the social sense has to be shown. These categories have so far been known to occur as official designations, and in the Egra copper-plate too they occur amidst known official titles (*vaiṣayika*, *karaṇika*, *pustapāla* and *sthāyīpāla*).⁶⁶

The graphic portrayal of the rural society in Bengal is matched by a rich description of the different social groups among the peasants in Kalikaṭṭi (pp. 106-10). For the Naḍḍula countryside, Chattopadhyaya finds no evidence for extra-brāhmaṇa/ temple/secular assignee differentiation: "In Godwad, the nature of stratification within the layer of cultivator-proprietors cannot be worked out ..." (pp. 77-78). Yet his own narrative provides several pointers: the lessees of land (pp. 80-81) must have been different from the general run of cultivator-proprietors working with their family their own pieces of land, and these in turn must have been distinguished from the *rathakāras* who could donate one *hāela* (that is, *hala*) of *javār*-producing land⁶⁷ (p. 77), the distinction probably corresponding to that between *grāmīnas* and *mahājanas* (ibid.). Yet another category could have consisted of the cultivators (*kuṭumbikas*) who were gifted (*pradatta*) along with their relatives or with their sons and grandsons (p. 81). These persons were themselves items of gift, lacking full control over their own person; we may not ascribe this dependent status to the common mass of peasants without the required evidence; the process the historians have observed was one of the growing subjection of the peasantry, and not of the progressive liberation of a subject peasantry.

64 *dhanakulādīna pahano. Niśītha-sūtram*, Part II (Agam Sahitya Ratnamala 4, Delhi, 1982), p. 101, cited in B.N.S. Yadava, "Historical Investigation into Social Terminology in Literature", *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, 53rd session (Warangal, 1992-93), p. 26, n. 101.

65 B.N. Sharma, *Social Life in Northern India, A.D. 600-1000* (Munshiram Manoharlal, New Delhi, 1966), p. 311, cited in R.S. Sharma, *Social Changes in Early Medieval India, circa A.D. 500-1200* (People's Publishing House, New Delhi, 1969), p. 16.

66 If the list in Appendix 3 (p. 67) follows the order of the record.

67 *yugamdharyāḥ hāela eka 1 pra(dattāḥ)*, *Epigraphia Indica*, Vol. XI, p. 47, l.4. Chattopadhyaya takes it to be "grain share" (p. 77), which is based on the belief of the record's editor D.R. Bhandarkar that the grant was of "one *hāela* (that is, as much land as could be tilled by a single plough in one day) of *yugamdhari* or *javār* corn" (op.cit., p. 147, emphasis added). The emphasis shows the incongruity of Bhandarkar's translation. The use of the land-measure *hāela* would show that the meaning of *yugamdharyāḥ hāela eka* was not "one *hāela* of *yugamdhari*" but "one *hāela* of *yugamdhari*-producing land". The importance of the grant of one *hāela* of land by a number of *rathakāras* together may be seen in the fact that in the same record the queen-mother of the king donates no more than the same quantity of the same type of land (ibid., ll. 1-2).

Chattopadhyaya's second point against the thesis that landgrants created a class of brāhmaṇa intermediaries and led to social cleavage between brāhmaṇas and the peasantry (p. 127) is that these "formulations ... do not explore the possibility that a section of the rural community could continue to remain dominant" (p. 45-46). He brings out "the levels at which the brāhmaṇas and categories of landholders are found in association with each other, at [to] the exclusion of other categories" (p. 17, n. 38) in early medieval Bengal: brāhmaṇas were already among the leading landholders and actively associated in the local affairs of the state along with the non-brāhmaṇa landholders (op.cit.), and even the brāhmaṇa *agrahārīnas* are placed in the Egra copper-plate together with—and not as lording over—*mahattaras*, *mahāmahattaras* and the like (p. 52).

Third, the Egra plate and the Mallasarul record carefully describe the role of the leading landholders from a number of villages including *agrahāras* in the land transactions, but they do not mention any person from the villages where the gift lands were situated (pp. 52-53). This shows a hierarchical division between villages having powerful landowners and "the comparatively insignificant" settlements (p. 52). We could also refer to the hierarchy represented by Palāśavṛndaka and Caṇḍagrāma villages, and hazard a guess about the "comparative insignificance". One obvious clue is that the more important villages had a group of influential landowners which the insignificant ones did not have. This would be supported by the reference to the residents of Caṇḍagrāma as *brāhmaṇādhyaḥśakṣudraprakṛtikūṭumbinaḥ*, "the husbandmen ... who are inferior ryots and presided over by the brāhmaṇas".⁶⁸ The hierarchy among the villages, the characterization of the cultivators in Caṇḍagrāma as "small" (*ksudraprakṛti*) and of brāhmaṇas as their "heads/masters" (*adhyaḥśa*), and Palāśavṛndaka having important *mahattaras* and *kūṭumbins* correspond very neatly to a pattern in traditional rural Bihar in modern times. In a survey "it was found that more often than not the villages of a particular locality were so clustered that a big, generally centrally located village having a number of castes served as a feeder while others were satellites depending in many ways on this".⁶⁹ There were two types of satellite villages; one (called satellite-B) was "most closely bound to age-old local convention and tradition".⁷⁰ In this village, "only a few families of one single caste (belonging either to the cluster of intermediate castes or to that of the lowest castes or to that of the lower Muslim groups) were reported to be residing without having land of their own" and "had only two occupations—*bataidari* and *janaouri*".⁷¹ *Bataidars* were sharecroppers and *janas* were bonded labourers or ploughmen; both addressed their landlords as *malik*⁷² (masters). The villagers see the rural society as divided in two categories: *baraka* and *chotaka/nanh*, literally "big" and "small".⁷³

The fourth point pertains to the manner in which increasing bureaucratization added to the hierarchy in rural society. This has been discussed above in the second section.

Fifth, the land allotments in the Paschimbhag plates (pp. 55-56, 67-69) show that even landgrants could make arrangements which had no use for the dichotomy between monolithic

⁶⁸ D.R. Bhandarkar et al, ed, *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, Vol. III, p. 336, l.3, p. 338. Earlier Basak and Sircar read this as *brāhmaṇādyannakṣudraprakṛtikūṭumbinaḥ*.

⁶⁹ Hetukar Jha, *Social Structures of Indian Villages: A Study of Rural Bihar* (Sage Publications, New Delhi, 1991), pp. 36-37, citing H. Jha and S. Gopal, "Classification of Indian Villages", *Man in India*, Vol. 62, No. 2 (1982), p. 125.

⁷⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 36.

⁷¹ *Ibid.*

⁷² *Ibid.*, chs 6,7.

⁷³ *Ibid.*, pp. 46-54, ch. 4.

brāhmaṇas and the undifferentiated rest : “while a teacher or a Vedic scholar attached to a *maṭha* was entitled to ten *pāṭakas* of land, other brāhmaṇas, even of the *mahattara* category, were not entitled to more than two *pāṭakas*. This was even less than the shares received by a Kāyastha and a Vaidya Similarly, carpenters, smiths and artisans were put far above other service communities in terms of their share in land” (p. 56).

3.3 Assessing the importance of landgrants: The case of Kalikaṭṭi

Chattopadhyaya does not merely locate the various lines of stratification in the rural society other than those caused by landgrants; he argues from his study of the conversion of Kalikaṭṭi into an *agrahāra* after about A.D.1215 that such conversions through landgrants did not lead to as momentous transformations as is often made out. He states:

All that we know—and that too only in a few cases—is that such conversions could create tension in the rural areas to the extent of forcing royal power to ruthlessly suppress resistance. But in the majority of cases it would be doubtful whether the creation of an *agrahāra* would drastically alter the social composition of the settlement, whatever other changes it may have brought about (p. 8).

Chattopadhyaya's position is further underlined in the statement that “the basic character as a rural settlement” of Kalikaṭṭi did not change drastically after its conversion into an *agrahāra* (p. 111) and is confirmed in his *Making* where the stratification caused by landgrants finds no place in his picture of “regional social stratification” in early medieval India.⁷⁴ This position may need reconsideration. Chattopadhyaya's argument is based not on “the majority of cases” but only on one case : that of Kalikaṭṭi (p. 16, n. 30). Kalikaṭṭi's conversion did lead to enough tension between the *mahājanas* (brāhmaṇa settlers of the *agrahāra*) and the temples to necessitate arbitration more than once (pp. 112-14). The point that such types of tension (between temples and brāhmaṇas, between brāhmaṇas, etc.) have largely been ignored by the historians (pp. 10-11) is more relevant here than the denial of tension *implied* in the first quote. The other point should in fact be that in Kalikaṭṭi's case the tension did not lead to violence (pp. 110-11). Finally, in assessing the significance of Kalikaṭṭi's conversion, we have to take into account the following: nine-tenth of the temples's income, computed in gold coins, is now transferred to the brāhmaṇa donees and the temples apparently cease to receive landgrants, turning to other sources of income (pp. 111-12); a dominant community of the village makes “public declarations of allegiance” to these brāhmaṇas (ibid.); and the evidence of land disputes between the temples and the brāhmaṇas (pp. 112-13).

4 Perspectives

Few can read all this without being struck by the perspicacity of Chattopadhyaya's perspective. His findings will have to be recognized and integrated in any general portrayal of early medieval India. Chattopadhyaya himself uses them to demolish a number of “conceptual and historiographical stereotypes” (p. 125) and provide us “an alternative mode” of social change.⁷⁵ We discuss the following: (i) the stereotype of the self-sufficient village; (ii)

74 “The Making”, pp. 24-28.

75 Ibid., p. 37.

stratification in the rural society; and (iii) the transformation of the early historical into the early medieval.

4.1 Meanings of self-sufficiency

The first stereotype is the concept of the self-sufficient village, which "in terms of its economy as well as its community structure... has been resurrected in the early medieval context in what may be called the Indian Feudalism formulation" (p. 8). The self-sufficiency of the "economy" is said to have resulted from the decline of exchange networks and the restrictions on the mobility of the villagers (pp. 8-9). Against this, he argues that it implies the doubtful thesis that the rural economy was previously based on commercial exchange (p. 8), and enters important caveats against an uncritical application of the *jajmani* model to understand service relationships in early medieval India (pp. 61-62). Next, self-sufficiency in terms of "community structure" apparently means (i) communal rights (p. 8) including co-ownership of soil (p. 16, n. 31) and (ii) "an undifferentiated community with no movement" (p. 9). It is the context of the thesis of communal ownership of land that enables us to see why he has provided detailed arguments (pp. 76-77) to establish that the "local resident stratum in rural society [in south-east Marwar]... owned both land and *araghattas*, not in the form of a village community but as individual members of the village society" (p. 76; see also p. 98). On the issue of communal rights, he finds R.S. Sharma hazy: Sharma perhaps meant by communal rights "agglomeration" of "'peasant units' of production" (p. 10), which was corroded by landgrants (pp. 8, 10, 45). The formulation is "somewhat facile" (p. 45). Finally, he is led on by his evidence for differentiation to reject the notion of village community: "If the residents of a village were differentiated in various ways, then constructing them into a 'community' would serve little purpose..."⁷⁶

We are not sure if the Indian Feudalism formulation includes the community structure of villages as an element in its construct of self-sufficiency. In fact, the communal structure of pre- and non-feudal villages stands counterpoised to their self-sufficiency in early medieval, feudal set-up. Next, Chattopadhyaya's treatment of Sharma's ideas on communal rights has been somewhat indifferent. There are two aspects of Sharma's exposition of communal rights in non-feudal villages. One is that "individual appropriation of land was subject to some effective communal control"⁷⁷ and it was by landgrants that individual ownership of land was created for the first time.⁷⁸ Argued and developed at some length,⁷⁹ the thesis is less simple-minded and better grounded empirically than the previous statements on the community structure; accordingly its critique has to be more detailed and complex than a simple denial of co-ownership of land. The second aspect relates to communal control of the land resources that were not individually possessed: pastures, trees, fisheries and the like. The evidence and the arguments for this have been very specific;⁸⁰ Chattopadhyaya's critique does not address them at all. Likewise, that rural settlements were previously a part of wider commercial network is

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 21, n. 44.

⁷⁷ *Indian Feudalism*, pp. 111-12; cf. K. Marx, *Capital*, Vol. III (Moscow, 1986), p. 791: "... no private ownership of land exists, although there is both private and common possession and use of land".

⁷⁸ *Indian Feudalism*, pp. 93-95.

⁷⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 91-98, 109, ch. IV; R.S. Sharma, *Perspectives in Social and Economic History of Early India* (Manoharan Manoharlal, New Delhi, 1983), pp. 136-37.

⁸⁰ *Indian Feudalism*, loc.cit.; also pp. 182-85.

not just an implication of the thesis of early medieval closed economy, but has actually been spelt out⁸¹ and the Paschimbhag plates have been used as evidence for *jajmani* system in early medieval Bengal.⁸² Chattopadhyaya's critique could have preferably been situated with reference to these delineations, for that alone would create common ground for dialogue. A critique must after all aim at creating a unity of discourse and this is best served by a most precise statement of the "adversary's" position. Last, divisions in the rural society led a number of sociologists to reject the notion of the village community, as Chattopadhyaya does. The rejection was fully logical, as the senses in which the village community had been conceived stood rebutted. Yet on reflection it was found that the connotations of the term "community" are not exhausted by those specific senses (village republic, lack of differentiation, etc.). So scholars have found it useful to retain the concept of village community to signify the many levels at which the village functions as a unit.⁸³ They retain it to denote the ways in which Chattopadhyaya himself conceives the identity of a village: "the ways in which individual villages figure as specific reference points in epigraphy, literature and other sources—as also in the life experiences of village residents" (p. 125). The differentiations show that there was no "amorphous" (p. 7) or "pristine"⁸⁴ village community; "the ways" show how we may conceive a village community none the less.

Villages in the past have also been seen as little republics. They are no longer seen as such, but Chattopadhyaya sees the prevalence of an analogous attitude. He finds the assumption common to the Indian Feudalism formulation and other approaches (such as Stein's) that "rural settlements... initially stand at a distance from political power"/"the state" prior to the state's granting of land or enlarging its revenue base (pp. 10, 128). As I see it, however, in the Indian Feudalism formulation the making of grants *presupposes* the inclusion of the villages in the ambit of state power⁸⁵ and the distancing of the area from the state (central authority) occurs *after* the grant.

The concept of the self-sufficient village, according to Chattopadhyaya, has prevented the historians from visualizing the "formation of inter-village network" (p. 9). This statement has to be qualified. In the Indian Feudalism formulation, there have been at least three unidentified

81 *Urban Decay*, pp. 148-49, 151, 166.

82 *Ibid.*, pp. 158-59.

83 D. Mandelbaum, *op.cit.*, pp. 327-37; Y. Singh, *The Modernization of Indian Tradition* (Thomson Press, Faridabad, 1973), pp. 184-87; M.N. Srinivas, *India: Social Structure*, reprint (Hindustan Publishing Corporation, Delhi, 1986), pp. 13-20, 42-45.

84 "The Making", p. 21.

85 It is this presupposition that has so far been a focus of criticism: "... before assuming alienation of royal power and resources through land donations to Brahmins and their endowment with immunities (*parihāra*) and privileges, one should always ask whether the royal donor had really been able to exercise all those powers himself which he transferred to the donee", H. Kulke, "Fragmentation and Segmentation *versus* Integration? Reflections on the Concepts of Indian Feudalism and the Segmentary State in Indian History", *Studies in History*, Vol. IV, No. 2 (1982), p. 247. It was doubted first by Stein ("The State and Agrarian Order", *op.cit.*, p. 88). The critique is effectively answered, and the presupposition vindicated, by the attempts at the forgery of landgrants in the name of the reigning monarch, the nullification of the forgeries by him (as by Harṣa), the instances of resumption of landgrants, of the restoration of the resumed grants by kings, and of issuing copper-plate charters when the original on leaves was lost or the original command, being oral, was not believed, besides the internal evidence of the charters themselves.

versions of the “closed economy” in early medieval India: (i) self-sufficiency of the village,⁸⁶ (ii) self-sufficiency of the locality consisting of a number of villages,⁸⁷ and (iii) self-sufficiency of the benefice which could vary from one village to an area spread over several villages to an area spread over several localities.⁸⁸ The latter two versions rest on inter-village networks. It is only by seeing the hypothesis of “closed economy” in the totality of the statements on it that we may appreciate its points of strength as well as weakness. Its strength lies in the good amount of evidence for the non-commercial exchange of goods and services in the temple and monastic complexes: various categories of artisans and other service groups were given plots of land in exchange for their services, while the peasants working on the land granted provided the necessary agricultural products. Among its weaknesses we may count the following:

(a) There is the assumption that grant of land to the temples, *brāhmaṇas* and the like dispenses with commercial exchange. The grant of land to the donees in villages instead of supporting them in the capital does decrease and simplify the circuit of surplus distribution, but by itself this does not tell us how the donees would meet their needs. It is the service grants that create a space for non-commercial exchange. The point is illustrated through the Paschimbhag inscription and the two Bhaumakara charters from Talcher in Dhenkanal district, both of which have been taken to demonstrate how the religious establishments “functioned as self-sufficient economic units in large measure”.⁸⁹ The Paschimbhag inscription refers to the grant of plots of land to florists, oilmen, potters, carpenters, masons, blacksmiths, sweepers, etc., for serving the *maṭhas*. Here we see the creation of a sector of non-commercial exchange, to the extent the services of these people were ensured on a hereditary and fixed basis. However, even these extensive arrangements did not fully meet the exchange requirements of the *maṭhas*, for even after these grants to the carpenters, masons, blacksmiths, etc., one hundred twenty-seven (fortyseven + eighty) *pāṭakas* of land had to be earmarked, out of a total of four hundred *pāṭakas*, for the maintenance of the *maṭha* buildings. Thus almost one-third of the income from the landgrants had to be spent through market exchange on the items which were not covered by securing the services of the oilmen, potters and so on. This was even more so in the second case, described in the Bhaumakara charters. They refer to the donation of two villages to a Buddhist temple and divide the income into three parts: one-third for the worship of the Buddha image by arranging lamp, incense, perfume, flower, etc; one-third for the repairs; and one-third for the maintenance of the *dānapati*. Obviously, the agricultural income from the two villages had to be given away in exchange for obtaining the materials for the worship, carrying out the repairs of the temple and meeting the sundry needs of the *dānapati*; there is no basis in the record for assuming that the

⁸⁶ R.S. Sharma, *Indian Feudalism*, pp. 52, 59, 103-4, 221-22; *Urban Decay*, pp. 166, 177, 184.

⁸⁷ *Indian Feudalism*, pp. 56-58, 105, 197-98. In *Urban Decay* (pp. 154-55) we see the hypothesis (based on inference from place-names) of immigrant artisans from the declining towns of Vidarbha founding villages of their own and serving the rural population. This is supposed to have made the “villages ... self-contained and self-reliant” (*ibid.*, p. 155), but this really is to argue for the self-sufficiency of the locality being served by artisan villages rather than that of each individual village. For the method involved in using place-names as evidence, see my review of K.M. Shrivastava, *Agrarian Structure in Central India and the Northern Deccan c.A.D. 300-500: A Study in Vākāṭaka Inscriptions* (Munshiram Manoharlal, New Delhi, 1987) in *Social Science Probings*, Vol. V, Nos 1-4 (1988), pp. 150-52.

⁸⁸ *Indian Feudalism*, pp. 52, 104-5, 222; *Urban Decay*, pp. 156-57, 158-60, 162-65.

⁸⁹ *Urban Decay*, pp. 158-60, 163-64, 165 (for the quote).

landgrants created a self-sufficient unit. Landgrants made substantial landlords of brāhmaṇas, temples and the like, investing them with expendable surplus and thus extending the scope of commerce in the countryside; they did not make them proof against the market, although the grants of plots to the service classes did create a *sector* of closed economy, that is, closed to the market.⁹⁰

(b) While we are offered the mechanism of *jajmani* exchange for the non-commercial economy of the village and the mechanism of landgrant for service relationships in a temple or monastic complex, we are not told how the self-sufficiency of a locality operated. Also the evidence for the prevalence of the *jajmani* system in the average village during the early medieval period is not really better than that for the pre-Gupta villages. Modern parallels scarcely help. *Jajmani* ties in recent times usually spread over several villages rather than being confined to one village,⁹¹ and so they do not make for village self-sufficiency, and are too limited in scope for a locality to make it self-sufficient. A similar conclusion against village self-sufficiency during the middle Cōḷa period can be drawn from the solid research of Noboru Karashima.⁹²

(c) Another grey area is the manner in which the self-sufficiencies of the village, of the locality and of the benefice relate to each other. The disarticulation comes out graphically when we see the same piece of evidence—grant of thousands of villages to the Somnath temple—being used at one place to argue for “the closed economy” of the Somnath establishment⁹³ and at another place to argue for the breakdown of the “closed economy” of the localities from where the villages were granted.⁹⁴ Here we also see a negative result of the influence of Henri Pirenne on Sharma’s *Indian Feudalism*: self-sufficiency only till the tenth century, market economy only thereafter.⁹⁵

4.2 Socio-economic divisions

Chattopadhyaya believes that the historians have so far seen the peasantry as an undifferentiated mass (p. 128) and they conceive rural stratification as a bipolar division between the brāhmaṇas

90 Cf. L. Dumont, *Homo Hierarchicus* (Paladin, London, 1972), pp. 138-39.

91 D. Mandelbaum, *op. cit.*, p. 172.

92 Noboru Karashima, *South Indian History and Society* (Oxford University Press, Delhi, 1984), pp. 40-55.

93 *Urban Decay*, pp. 165, 167.

94 *Indian Feudalism*, pp. 197-98.

95 Likewise, the descriptions emphasizing money economy in pre-Gupta period have not taken into account the contemporary evidence of barter exchange (see R. Thapar, *A History of India*, Penguin Books, 1990, pp. 112-13; Balram Srivastava, *Trade and Commerce in Ancient India*, Chowkhambha Sanskrit Series, Varanasi, 1968, pp. 304-8).

None of this, however, will justify the charge that Sharma’s version of early medieval Indian economy has been a *carbon-copy* of Pirenne’s model (H. Mukhia, “Peasant Production and Medieval Indian Society”, in his *Perspectives on Medieval History* (Vikas Paperbacks, New Delhi, 1994, p. 164). Only the inspiration was Pirenne’s; the thesis itself rests on considerable research, providing in fact the only detailed general picture of the times; it stands or falls on its own empirical worth. The manner in which alternative approaches to early medieval Indian economic history have been situated in relation to Sharma’s work (J.S. Deyell, *Living Without Silver*, Oxford University Press, Delhi, 1990, pp. 11-12; Chattopadhyaya’s papers) attests its importance. Second, Indian historians had already perceived a phase of decline of commerce and urban centres in Indian history without any discernible influence of Pirenne. Thus when in 1965 Irfan Habib wrote about the postulate of decline in urban life and the paucity of coins, he referred to Kosambi and K.K. Gopal (*Enquiry*, Vol. II, No. 3, 1965, pp. 40-41). Still earlier, in 1949, Niharranjan Ray too wrote about the decline in commerce (personal communication from Professor B.D. Chattopadhyaya).

and the peasantry, "broadly speaking" (p. 10). The meaning of "broadly speaking" is seen on p. 128 when he refers to "the somewhat simplistic picture of brāhmaṇa-dominated rural society, or, at the most, of a society polarised between the local lords, the *bhogikas*, the *ṭhakkuras* and an undifferentiated mass of common residents" (emphasis added). There is no concession that the historians before him may have recognized divisions among the peasants. This becomes clearer from a statement of D.N. Jha he picks up to demonstrate how the blindness of the historians to extra-brāhmaṇa (local lord) stratification has been total: "Jha points to the growing stratification within the peasantry itself, but does not elaborate; the 'social cleavage' he talks about is between the brāhmaṇas and the peasantry" (p. 17, n. 38).⁹⁶

It is possible to question the accuracy of Chattopadhyaya's statements. Sharma has frequently noted the divisions among the peasantry during the early medieval period.⁹⁷ Jha no doubt goes on to describe brāhmaṇa-peasant polarity in the paragraph which he starts with a reference to the growing differentiation among the peasantry, as Chattopadhyaya points out. But the following paragraphs are devoted to the evidence for internal stratification among the peasantry, and the better-off peasants are identified as one of the four groups of the landed intermediaries.⁹⁸

Yet the imprecise statements of Chattopadhyaya are inspired by a correct impression, which is that interest in stratification among the peasants has been marginal to the concerns of the historians, who have mainly been interested in the formation of intermediaries between the state and the peasant masses. Sharma described the *mahattaras* in the Gupta period landgrants as village elders in 1968 in his *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions*.⁹⁹ In 1969 he spoke of them as "a class of village elders and headmen", "substantial" landholders.¹⁰⁰ In 1987 in *Urban Decay* he discussed in detail the same set of evidence and concluded that the *mahattaras* were not village elders but were better-off peasants.¹⁰¹ Yet in 1991 when he brought out the revised and expanded edition of the *Aspects of Political Ideas*, he continued to call them "village elders", as he did in the previous edition.¹⁰² And in 1992 he described them alternately as "rich substantial peasants" and "village elders" in the same paragraph.¹⁰³ This cannot be dismissed as a lapse on his part, for a consistent attention to the precise connotation of technical terms has been a notable feature of his scholarship. Thus when he revised his understanding of the term *bhāgadugha* in the later Vedic literature, he duly noted that and gave reasons for the revision,¹⁰⁴ and, eight years later, took care to include the revision in his *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions*. The only

⁹⁶ Citing p. 79 from D.N. Jha, "Relevance of Peasant State and Society to Pallava - Cōla Times", *The Indian Historical Review*, Vol. VIII, Nos 1-2 (July 1981 and January 1982), pp. 74-94.

⁹⁷ R.S. Sharma, *Indian Feudalism*, p. 85 ("The mention of only the village elders in the grants presupposes some social stratification in the rural area"); idem, *Social Changes in Early Medieval India*, pp. 16-17; idem, *Urban Decay*, pp. 175-76; idem, "Problems of Peasant Protest in Early Medieval India", *Social Scientist* (September 1988), p. 3.

⁹⁸ D.N. Jha, op.cit., pp. 80-83.

⁹⁹ *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions in Ancient India*, 2nd edn (Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1968), pp. 245, 246, 247, 253, 300.

¹⁰⁰ *Social Changes in Early Medieval India*, pp. 16-17.

¹⁰¹ *Urban Decay*, pp. 175-76.

¹⁰² *Aspects of Political Ideas and Institutions in Ancient India*, 3rd edn (1991), pp. 331, 333, 339, 388. There is evidence that this section was included in the revision.

¹⁰³ Idem, "Antiquity to the Middle Ages in India", *Social Science Probings*, Vol. V, Nos 1-4, p. 28.

¹⁰⁴ *Material Culture and Social Formations in Ancient India* (Macmillan, Delhi, 1983), pp. 76, 87, n. 63.

way we can explain his treatment of the term *mahattara* is to see the issue as marginal to his concern. Jha's interest in differentiation among the peasantry too arises out of his central concern with the intermediaries and their varied origins. So the peasantry in the Indian Feudalism construct has not been studied as a subject in itself, but mainly in relation to its generalized subjection by the intermediaries, although it is not true that there has been an assumption of undifferentiated peasantry. This is not negated by the valuable recent study of Yadava where he discusses the import of several terms denoting various types of peasants. His is a study of terms, not of social structure, and is no more relevant to our judgement on the historiography than is Sircar's *Indian Epigraphical Glossary*.

Chattopadhyaya also offers us his own version of "regional social stratification"¹⁰⁵ in early medieval India, as contrapuntal to the prevailing concern with the landed intermediaries.¹⁰⁶ He refers in detail to his own discussions of *kuṭumbins*, *mahattaras*, etc., in Bengal and the *prabhugāvunḍas*, *prajāgāvunḍas*, etc., in Karnataka as well as to the works on the many cultivating groups in Assam and the "extensive continuum from such groups as the Paraiyar to the upper echelons of the dominant Vellāla" in Tamil Nadu¹⁰⁷ to the complete exclusion of the land grantees: "In the period identified as early medieval, it was... the changes from within localities and regions which *alone* can point to the ways in which not only were regional communities transformed but were hierarchized as well".¹⁰⁸ He goes on to state that the early medieval period represents "a crucial phase in the evolution of regional *agrarian structures*", apparently because we see then the appearance of "the majority of *regionally recognizable* cultivating groups, such as the Gurjaras, Kaivartas, Gāvunḍas, Reḍḍis, Kalitas".¹⁰⁹ Here the assumption of regional identity by the peasants is made the distinguishing criterion of early medieval regional agrarian structures while the landlords created through landgrants are kept out of the picture.

In saying all this, Chattopadhyaya calls attention to the categories and processes which have so far been largely neglected. Yet as a general conception, his generalizations on early medieval agrarian structure remain deficient in their ignoring the significance of landgrants. In place of assimilating the ground covered by Sharma, Yadava and others, he seeks to create a general picture out of the themes they did not attend. When he reports about his research into the agrarian structure in early medieval Karnataka, he refers to *prajāgāvunḍas*, *prabhugāvunḍas* and *sāmantas*; he omits the temple and the group of *mahājanas*, although his research furnishes detailed evidence about them as substantial landholders. The omission is comprehensible only in terms of his reaction to the Indian Feudalism construct. He has spoken of the regional societies of early medieval India having a pan-Indian character;¹¹⁰ one could insist that it is the land grantees that provide a pan-Indian stamp to the regional agrarian structures and enable us to speak of an early medieval Indian agrarian structure that was different from the early historical.

In other words, Chattopadhyaya's portrayal of early medieval Indian agrarian structure

105 "The Making", p. 27.

106 *Ibid.*, pp. 10-11.

107 *Ibid.*, pp. 26-27.

108 *Ibid.*, p. 25, n. 56.

109 *Ibid.*, pp. 27-28 (emphases added).

110 *Ibid.*, p. 17.

underplays the importance of landgrants in the same way as his understanding of Kalikaṭṭi's social structure does that of its conversion into an *agrahāra*. It is tempting to polemicize the point, take the next logical step and state that the significance of Kalikaṭṭi's conversion into an *agrahāra* brings out the significance of landgrants in general, that Chattopadhyaya's scheme does not so much negate Sharma's design as complements it and that we can obtain the total picture by simply putting the two together. We wish to take a different position.

For Sharma and Jha, landgrants lead to the formation of a single category of landlords, the "landed intermediaries": whether it is the grant of a plot of land to one brāhmaṇa, a village to a brāhmaṇa, or the grant of a village to, say, one hundred brāhmaṇas; all create a single category of feudal lords, whether they are given land free from taxes or they are given taxes. The fundamental concern has been to bring out the formation of a category intermediate between the state and the peasants (the brāhmaṇa donee of even a small plot is not expected to till it himself). The result has been a loose usage of rigorously distinct categories: the brāhmaṇa recipients of *agrahāras* can, together with dominant Vellālas, form the category of "dominant peasantry" at one place¹¹¹ while at another they all can be called feudal intermediaries exploiting a subject peasantry;¹¹² with equal aplomb, the *mahattaras* and others can be placed among the intermediaries¹¹³ distinct from the peasants and at another place can be assimilated among the better-off peasants.¹¹⁴

"Stratification"/"hierarchy" is to Chattopadhyaya what "intermediary" is to Sharma and Jha. All groups which are distinguished from each other in the sources become for Chattopadhyaya several groups in a stratified system: *mahattaras*, *mahāmahattaras*, *kuṭumbins*, etc., in Bengal; *bhūmiputrakas*, *prajāgāvundās*, *prabhugāvundās*, *sāmantas*, etc., in Karnataka, and so on. His categories are enumerative, with no discussion of the distinguishing criteria. It is true that for the most part we have little precise data on their wealth, status, place in the production system, and so on. The point, however, is that no attempt is made even to raise these issues, and take into account such indications as we have. With a wealth of detail, he has been able to establish—which none did before him—that "the structure of... village society was much more complex than simple polarisation" (p. 128); the *structure* of the complexity, however, remains unexplored. In the context of the polity, he characterizes a regional state society with "a complex of relations of domination and subordination",¹¹⁵ but does not bring it to bear on his depiction of agrarian structures. He refers to these groups as forming a "hierarchy" in a "continuum". The terms imply the existence of a single scale in which different groups hold different positions: *mahattaras* differing from *kuṭumbins* in the same way in which *sāmantas* differ from *kuṭumbins*, for example. Consistently enough, he conceives of the agrarian structure in terms of "several cultivating groups" and does not bring in landlords, for landlords would not form a continuum with the cultivating groups. Landlords, however, may easily be detected among his groups: the relation of a *prabhugāvunḍa* or a *sāmanta* (or the temple or the *mahājanas* for that matter) to the several *gāvunḍa* groups and other peasant communities was demonstrably different (p. 106) from the relation between these latter groups (pp. 106-10) while yet another type of relation

111 D.N. Jha, op.cit., p. 81.

112 Ibid., pp. 82, 92 and n. 3.

113 R.S. Sharma, "Problems of Peasant Protest", op.cit., p. 3.

114 R.S. Sharma, *Urban Decay*, pp. 175-76.

115 "The Making", p. 21.

would prevail between the *prabhugāvunḍa*, the *sāmanta*, the temple and the *mahājanas* (whether direct or mediated through the state).

When in 1992 Sharma rewrote and expanded his 1974 article on the transition from ancient to medieval in Indian history, he attempted to find a place for *mahattaras* and *kuṭumbins* in his scheme thus:

... apart from the landed beneficiaries or the agents of the king who were entitled to rent or tax, as the case may be, the rural areas came to have two strata consisting of the *mahattara* on the top and the *kuṭumbins* below them. Of course the land assignees formed a higher rung in the rural ladder.¹¹⁶

Here the relation between *kuṭumbins* and *mahattaras* is conceived as of the same type as between either and the landed intermediaries; each category forms a “rung in the rural ladder”.

Not to put too fine a point on it, the conceptual distinction between rich peasantry, landlord and feudal landlord has had no systematic application in our historiography. Their usefulness, known from the historiographies elsewhere, is reinforced by the inadequacies of our methods of analysis. When we see that a *mahattara* could be resourceful enough to control the entire pasture of a village while a *mahattara* elsewhere was only one among the numerous big landowners in a village; that *agrahārīnas* sat together with *mahattaras* apparently as equals in a charter while the grantees in the *Harṣacarita* could make the *mahattaras* receive the king with pitchers on their heads;¹¹⁷ and that one “landed intermediary” owned a small patch of tax-free *khila* land while another “landed intermediary” enjoyed the entire fiscal resources of and administrative authority over a village, we must cease to employ these categories as discrete units in the economic structure of early medieval India. We must use them not as ends in themselves, but as sources for our own categories, if we are to understand the early medieval economies through comparison: no comparison of early medieval Bengal’s agrarian structure is possible otherwise with those of Karnataka and Rajasthan, much less with Mughal or medieval French or Chinese ones, and the result would be progressive atomization (early medieval Bengal economy, early medieval South Karnataka economy, early medieval Kalikaṭṭi economy, and so on).

4.3 The making of early medieval India

Finally, we discuss Chattopadhyaya’s perspectives on the transition from the early historical to the early medieval period of Indian history. He criticizes the attempts to explain the transition in terms of the decentralization of the Mauryan state and the crisis of the Kali Age. He thinks that such attempts posit the “breakdown” or “collapse” of the early historical order as the people supposedly refused to pay taxes and obey their superiors. He prefers to see early medieval India as a period in which regional societies emerged as the composite product of three connected processes: state formation, peasantization of tribes and integration of local cults into the brāhmaṇical fold. Further, the process of state formation is significant only as local state formation. In the end, the issue whether this period may or may not be termed feudal is considered to be marginal to his exercise.

Chattopadhyaya’s distrust of the Kali Age crisis theory seems quite valid to us, although he

116 R.S. Sharma, “Antiquity to the Middle Ages in India”, op.cit., p. 29.

117 Cited in R.S. Sharma, *Indian Feudalism*, p. 24.

initially gave his reasons somewhat pithily ("the historical roots of the 'crisis' are not clear"),¹¹⁸ which was replied in the like manner ("the passages, when they occur first, cannot be dismissed as figments of imagination").¹¹⁹ Chattopadhyaya has recently made a more detailed critique of the empirical as well as the explanatory status of the theory.¹²⁰ This must be reckoned with in any future statement on the Kali Age crisis, although Chattopadhyaya's critique too should have covered the arguments about the epigraphic validation of the Purāṇic accounts.¹²¹ The one problem with this theory which I find insuperable is this: How could the social crisis in a nuclear region be resolved by granting land in the outlying regions?¹²²

The Kali Age crisis theory, however, does not posit a "collapse" or "breakdown" of the early historical civilization, as has been alleged. It has been invoked to explain the *gradual transformation* of the early historical society through landgrants. It seeks to comprehend change through contradictions in the preceding structure rather than through its dramatic termination. Whatever its other faults, the theory is certainly not to be faulted on this score.

Chattopadhyaya attaches a special significance to the process of "local state formation". He distinguishes between "local states" and "regional state structures"¹²³ and between these two types and the still larger "territorial kingdoms".¹²⁴ He points out: "It is sharp fissions within communities and regions and the emergence of a complex of relations of domination and subordination which characterize a *regional state society*".¹²⁵ These ideas are applied thus: "As a region, early historical Vidarbha was a part of the major territorial kingdom of the Sātavāhanas, but the local state of Vidarbha, with an extensive agrarian base, came into existence only in the form of Vākāṭaka lineage from the middle of the third century A.D."¹²⁶

This emphasis on the importance of the Vākāṭaka state creates problems. The first is a minor, semantic one: Vidarbha is spoken of both as a "region" and as having a "local state". More important, are we to deny the state society in Vidarbha during the Sātavāhana period "the complex of relations of domination and subordination which characterize(s) a regional state society" and "an extensive agrarian base"?

Chattopadhyaya gives us an additional reason why he "picked on the process of *local state formation*": "This is because when studied in the context of its *local manifestation*, state formation makes intelligible a wide range of relationships, whereas discussions regarding the state from 'the stratosphere of a rarefied concept' rarely succeed in grasping such relationships".¹²⁷ This quote brings out the fallacy in the idea of emphasizing local state formation. State

¹¹⁸ "Political Processes", op.cit., p. 195, n. 29.

¹¹⁹ R.S. Sharma, "Problems of Social Protest in Early Medieval India", op.cit., p. 3. The reply was made without explicit reference to Chattopadhyaya.

¹²⁰ "State and Economy in North India: Fourth Century to Twelfth Century", in Romila Thapar, ed, *Recent Perspectives of Early Indian History* (Popular Prakashan, Bombay, 1995), pp. 329-31.

¹²¹ D.N. Jha, *Economy and Society in Early India: Issues and Paradigms* (Munshiram Manoharlal, New Delhi, 1993), pp. 69, 87, n. 24.

¹²² Cf. *ibid.*, p. 69; and H. Kulke, "Introduction: The Study of the State in Pre-modern India" in Kulke, ed *The State in India, 1000-1700*, p. 13.

¹²³ "The Making", p. 18.

¹²⁴ *Ibid.*, pp. 18, 19.

¹²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 21 (emphasis added).

¹²⁶ *Ibid.*, pp. 17-18.

¹²⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 19 (emphases added).

formation in its local manifestation (Vidarbha during Sātavāhana rule, Bengal during Gupta rule) is not the same as local state formation (Vākāṭaka state, Pāla state). The extension of state society is not equivalent to local dynastic rule.

The core thesis that regional societies were a distinguishing feature of early medieval India creates problems for early historical India by denying it its regional and local entities. What was the spatial unit in which the processes of state formation, cult assimilation and caste formation operated during the early historical period, if it was not region and locality? The denial is implicit in statements such as this: "... the transformation of early historical *society* took the form of the gradual shaping of regional *societies*..."¹²⁸ A more precise statement would perhaps be that the regions which emerged during the early medieval period are still with us: we can still recognize them as regions as we would not recognize the sixteen *mahājanapadas* (with exceptions like Magadha). The criterion for separating the early historical period from the early medieval period is their differing relations with the modern period. It has been followed earlier too, such as by Vincent A. Smith,¹²⁹ and it helps if we recognized it as such.

However, to confine attention to spatial distinctions between the two periods is to ignore the differences in socio-economic and political structures between them, and this must be considered a major limitation of Chattopadhyaya's synthesis. He has accepted the thesis of the emergence of a new political structure¹³⁰ and of the overall decline of urban centres,¹³¹ and has not denied the changes in the socio-cultural institutions. But these have been incidental to his main concern, which has been to make serious criticisms of the existing accounts. It is this preoccupation which, along with his concern with the regional dimensions of socio-cultural change, would seem to account for his failure to integrate the structural changes, the ground covered by Sharma and others, in his "Making of Early Medieval India".

It could also explain the way Chattopadhyaya distances himself from the feudalism debate: ... how do we respond to the schema of periodization which envisages an early medieval phase in the Indian context; also what is our response to the notion of an Indian feudal society as characterizing that phase? Since the main concerns of the present exercise have been with historiography, and with delineating the directions taken by the transformation of early historical society, these problems seem marginal to this exercise.¹³²

128 Ibid., p. 35 (emphases added).

129 According to Smith, the end of Harṣa's reign marked the dividing line between ancient and medieval India, the pre-Muslim period being "early medieval times". He could not see any institutional change and clearly stated: "The real difference between the ancient and the medieval periods is that the living tradition concerning the former has been broken, while that concerning the latter survives. The Mauryas and the Guptas belong to a dead and buried past, remembered only through books, inscriptions and coins, whereas the clans whose ruling families came into notice during the medieval period are still very much alive, and in many cases form numerous and influential sections of the existing population". He ascribed "the break in tradition" mainly to the Hun invasions, V. A. Smith. *The Early History of India*, 4th edn (Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1962; first published in 1924), pp. 423-27. These remarks should modify some of the recent judgements on the historiography of periodization of Indian history and help to answer such questions as why H.C. Raychaudhuri chose to end his political history of ancient India with the Guptas and H.C. Ray chose to call post-Harṣa period "early medieval".

130 Supra.

131 See my review of V.K. Thakur, *Historiography of Indian Feudalism* (Patna, 1989) in *The Indian Historical Review*, Vol. XVII, Nos 1-2 (July 1990 and January 1991), pp. 231-33; B.D. Chattopadhyaya, "Urban Centres in Early Medieval India: An Overview", in his *The Making of Early Medieval India*, pp. 159-60, 167.

132 "The Making", pp. 35-36.

We would say the opposite for the same reasons. If Chattopadhyaya's concern is the ways in which the early historical society was transformed, he must go beyond the issue of region formation to consider whether the new political and social formations were feudal or not. Avoiding the term "feudal" is not helpful, for it can mean accepting either the irrelevance of such categories or the critiques of the prevalent usages. Or it can mean that Chattopadhyaya has reasons for considering the issues still undecided and hence open. Whatever it is, there is no way he can deny us the benefit of his judgement.